

Open Up Digital Editions

Zurich
24.–26.
01.2024

Abstract

auf "ds" (42).
Fanno osservazioni Pisani e Grilli.
La seduta viene tolta alle ore 17.30.

SEDUTA DEL 26-3-1949.

La seduta è aperta alle ore 15.30.
Presenti: Casale, Caserio, Cusack-Grassi, Evangelisti, Grilli, Maspero, Menghini, Parangelli, Piatti, Pisani, Radice, Ramello, Sacchetti, Sovani, Tosoli, Predeci Pisani.
Si propone del presidente, vicedirettore socio ordinario il prof. Carlo Grönunger dell'Università di Milano, si dà poi lettura di altre adesioni al Congresso di lavoro. Su proposta del socio Grilli, il comma 3 dello statuto viene così integrato: «La Direzione dei nuovi soci verrà effettuata nella seduta seguente a quella della loro presentazione».

COMUNICAZIONI:

leben¹⁶, also daß wir in den fußstapfen dißers seines sohns heryn¹⁷ wandletind¹⁸. Der selb aber hat unß ernstlich¹⁹ gelehrt, die wält und theen fürsten mit sambe seinem rych der finsternuß Bühen und die himmelichen ding annehmen, simal²⁰ wir sterbliche menschen gar ein kurze zeit uff erden läbend und aber deß fleisches und der sünden lohn der ewig todt ist, deß geist aber und der tugent ewigs leben. Darumb je noht ist, daß wir alle, die in dem nammen gotes getaufft sind und in in durch Jeßum Christum

... wie er sy beschirmen
... groser süße²¹ deß geists, in aller
... dan je in dißem stand sich alle tugenten üben
... hoffmertzigkeit, hoffnung, gedult, mäßigkeit, zucht²² und
... hertzo Jesu unßeren herren. Darumb wir auch sehend, daß die
... uerthürvesten fründ gotes [Jak 2.23] in keinem anderen dan diem
... habent, allß Adam²³, Enoch²⁴, Abraham²⁵, Isaac²⁶, Jacob²⁷, Joseph²⁸,
... Aron²⁹, Josue³⁰, Gedeon³¹, Samuel³², David³³, Isajas³⁴ und im newen testament
... Petrus³⁵, Paulus³⁶, Philippus³⁷, kurz gar nach³⁸ alle ußerwehnen gotes sammenthaft³⁹;
... auch uff den übrighen töchteren beider testamenten Sara⁴⁰, Rebecca⁴¹, Lea⁴²
... Anna⁴³, Judith⁴⁴, Hester⁴⁵, Elisabetha⁴⁶ und die muter unsers erlößers
... welche doch in der ehe allein ein einige ewige port⁴⁷ und
... wie in ihren Isajas [7.14] gewyßiget hat und Ezechiel⁴⁸, je daß wir
... gemind, daß kein tugentlicher, kein gödlicher, kein fründlicher und
... lustbarer stand nit⁴⁹ ist dan der ehelich. Dan waß ist also heilig und züchig, waß ist also
... tugentlich und lieblich, daß die gotes fründ [Jak 2.23] nit gewürt haben? Hetend sy ein
... beßeren und seel[ig]eren stand gewürt vor got, so betend sie den selben angenommen.
... Sie habend aber in der ehe gelebt, so sol sich niemans uff den Christen merken lassen,
... sam⁵⁰ eß nit seie ein lieblicher gödlicher stand, ehelich syn.

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dhäyasam	0	root	-	-	-
Number=Plur Person=1 Tense=Past	3	nmod	-	-	-
Number=Masc Number=Sing	1	xcomp	-	-	-
Number=Masc Number=Sing	1	obj	-	-	-
Case=Acc Gender=Masc Number=Sing	4	amod	-	-	-
Number=Masc Number=Sing	0	root	-	-	-
Tense=Past	3	nmod	-	-	-
Number=Masc Number=Sing	1	xcomp	-	-	-
Number=Masc Number=Sing	1	obj	-	-	-

Photo Annemarie Schwarzenbach by Anita Forrer, © Swiss Literary Archives, Berne

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**University of
Zurich** ^{UZH}

**University
of Basel**

Library
University of Zurich

Call for Papers

In recent years, numerous innovative digital scholarly edition (DSE) projects have been implemented in Switzerland. The result is a growing scientific community. With the growing number of digital editions and the continuous availability of new edition data, issues of use and re-use are increasingly coming to the fore. However, many questions remain open and unresolved: Do editions meet the research needs? Which standards should future projects adopt? How do digital editions remain accessible after the end of the project? How can edition projects be linked with each other? These questions are of great concern to researchers, infrastructure providers and knowledge management institutions. The conference will provide a framework to discuss current approaches with a focus on developments in Switzerland and in relation to the international landscape.

We invite researchers from all disciplines as well as librarians, archivists, IT specialists and other stakeholders to contribute to the conference. Papers and posters on the following topics are welcome:

- Sources and models of editions: critical, genetic, diplomatic, documentary, social, etc.
- Minimal editions and prototypical workflows
- Machine learning in scholarly editing
- Editions and Linked Open Data
- Editions and APIs
- Long term preservation of data
- Maintenance of interfaces by whom, where, until when and how
- Linking, aggregations and search
- Use and reuse of editions in research and beyond
- Digital scholarly editions in archives and libraries
- Data stewardship, research support and digital scholarly editions

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Paper Sessions

Opening Up Scholarly Observation Of Textual Phenomena: A Fundamental Proposal

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Digital textual scholarship in the last decades has come a long way in realising sustainable access to open digital scholarly editions. As a de facto standard TEI-XML (Cummings 2012) provides a template for projects, processes, and models for the creation of digital scholarly texts. Ideally, adhering to FAIR principles ensures findability and access (cf. Helling, Jung, and Pielström 2022). Ubiquitous institutional hardware and cloudware together with, for instance, XML, HTML, and JSON serialisation guarantee longevity of digital texts (Digital Preservation Coalition 2015; The Endings Project Team 2023). RDF provides a means of interlinking data or factoids from digital editions (Oldman, Doerr, and Gradmann 2015). Virtualization offers a means of sustaining digital scholarly editions as graphical interfaces and applications (Rosenthal 2015). Methods of review have evolved (e.g. Sahle and Vogeler 2014). Perceived problems of sustainability and openness are technicalities – important technicalities, but technicalities nonetheless. However, digital scholarly editions face a paramount problem of a much more fundamental scientific nature.

Recently a number of articles in adjacent domains show how researchers in computational linguistics and computational literary research are struggling with problems of concretely binding theory to data observation (cf. Pichler and Reiter 2022; Bode 2023). We contend that digital textual scholarship struggles with the same problem at the intersection of the scholarly and the technical, because textual scholars only ever loosely and implicitly acknowledge what signs they are talking about when they express interpretations and inferences. This causes an elementary information imprecision that propagates to all interpretational levels, inciting infrastructural disputes that are commonly solved by entrenching technical and philosophical dogmas about texts. To solve this problem, we need to transform our scholarship into sets of operations that univocally, uniformly, and uniquely connect theory to data – and this should start with agreeing upon a universal system of addressing textual phenomena in sufficiently granular detail.

For perfectly understandable technical reasons at the time, historically the basic fabric that most of our scholarly specific digital technology works upon has been plain text files (including e.g. XML formats allowing to add structure and annotation). These represent text as unidirectional single character streams (Unicode Consortium 2021:18-19). The idea of all markup languages is that observations that are poorly expressed by such streams and any comments or specific interpretations can be added to the text as annotations (Burnard 1998). However, all forms of markup run into problems of representing textual complexities. A long history of publications has been dedicated to the inabilities and infeasibilities of TEI-XML and the possible fixes and workarounds (cf. for instance, Buzzetti 2002; DeRose 2004; Haentjens and Bimbaum 2017). Others have proposed standoff solutions that solve some problems (Tennison and Piez 2002; Haentjens, Bleeker and Buitendijk 2018) to find themselves troubled by new ones, as standoff solutions are notoriously brittle in case of changes to the original stream.

We argue that most of the technical problems we deal with in digital textual scholarship originate in the uncritical adoption of the string as the most basic expression of text. Most of these problems arise as artefacts of the technical properties of the character stream rather than as properties of textual and documentary concepts. As scholars of text we need to rethink the most fundamental building blocks of digital text expression. This requires a thoroughly science-philosophical and text theoretically reasoned approach that lets itself be guided much less by the make up and properties of digital primitive types.

For this we follow Pichler and Reiter (2022) who argue that theoretical principles need to be broken down into sets of operations that bridge the gap between scholarship and data. Likewise Katherine Bode argues that we need to stop separating computational from analog reasoning, so that scholarly inference arises from a true merging of the two approaches to computational literary research (Bode 2023). Bode as well as Pichler and Reiter invite us to use computation as an unequivocal expression of theory, no matter if one applies quantitative or qualitative methods. We argue that digital textual scholarship hitherto has poorly defined the processes and operations that identify precisely the textual objects its

scholarship is about. The challenge we face in computational textual scholarship is therefore twofold: we need to break down theory in operationalizable moves, but doing so –we contend– requires textual data to be concretely and unambiguously addressable in much more granular ways than we are currently used to.

We assert that the first-principle observation in textual scholarship is the identification of a sign. The sign will often be material, but may also be an electronic or digital representation. We show that in the case of a physical sign it is perfectly possible and feasible to address every glyph on a digital representation of a page with a URI and minimally sufficient metadata. We also argue that we must do so as digital textual scholars to unequivocally identify the signs we want to talk about: from a computational and digital textual scholarship point of view it is imprecise and inaccurate to do otherwise.

Following through this principal process of uniquely addressing each and every glyph results in a set of URIs. It follows that a base digital representation of any physical text ought to be a set of URIs and not a series of character codes. In computational terms we merely add another indirection, but one that will allow us to solve many problems that are currently considered common problems in digital textual scholarship, and one that opens up digital scholarly editions in many more ways for computational processing. We will demonstrate conceptually how this approach solves the problem of overlap, the problem of expressing the multidimensionality of text, and the problem of capturing precise provenance. We will also demonstrate how the suggested approach allows for progressive granularity of the textual description, which may be needed, for instance, in the case of paleographic description and annotation.

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Pivot and Derivative Data Formats as Approaches to Interoperability in Digital Scholarly Editions

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INTRODUCTION

Generic markup languages designed for or employed in the creation of digital scholarly editions (DSE) are almost always faced with the grand challenge that they are expected to be usable for encoding any form of text, irrespective of writing, sign system or genre, and from all historical epochs. The TEI Guidelines have proven that they are up to the challenge. However, this comes with a heavy price: the flexibility of the TEI Guidelines, when combined with project specific requirements, have led to the phenomenon that the majority of DSE projects generate research data that run counter to some of the founding ideas of TEI, especially with regard to the interoperability of data beyond the scope of a single project.¹ Touching the question of if and how this is a problem, the views of communities of practice tend to be very heterogeneous, as are the envisioned mitigation strategies.²

While using generic customisations might ensure a higher degree of interoperability from the get-go, this often sets very narrow limits for the project in terms of editorial modelling and implementation. To gain the best from both approaches – adequate encoding and interoperability – generic TEI customisations can be used as pivot formats to convert project-specific data into and store as supplementary data. In this case, interoperability is only achieved indirectly and at the cost of more resource investment, but at the same time grants projects more editorial freedom.

PIVOT AND DERIVATIVE DATA FORMATS

In the context of the CLARIAH-DE project (2019-21) the base format of the German Text Archive (DTABf) was evaluated in its suitability as a potential pivot format applicable to DSE in particular (Fisseni et al. 2021).³ Based on existing edition data, the encoding was assessed with regard to its interoperability and its potential for being transferred to the DTABf. The study showed the challenges and limitations of using a pivot format – information often can only be partially preserved and sometimes not at all. It also allowed to draw conclusions about re-use scenarios in which pivot formats can be employed usefully. Besides creating an output that might be displayed in generic viewers, one other likely scenario of use is that these data can serve as corpus texts or base for computational linguistic research.⁴ In certain domains, data in a simple pivot format can serve these purposes better than plain texts, but in both cases it does not mirror the original encoding. Considering these transformation scenarios is a necessary precondition for a responsible management of research data.⁵

Yet there are other possibilities for opening up editions that also can be tackled without major effort. An example of this would be the creation and provision of BEACON files, which list the GND numbers of persons appearing in an edition. Existing tools (including so-called “see also”-services or various BEACON finders) can be used to make retrievals across various kinds of resources. (see figure 1) Further, the application of BEACON is not limited to specific authority data providers or types of entities, neither by principle nor by format or technology. While BEACON files collect identifiers

¹Concerning TEI-based editions, Syd Bauman discussed the problem of interoperability and expressivity. Cf. Bauman 2011. Schmidt 2014 addresses different uses of the TEI as hindrances of interoperable editions. He pleads for a standoff solution by separating plain text, markup, annotations, and metadata. In recent years, the topic got new impetus from the publication of the FAIR principles. Cf. Wilkinson et al. 2016.

²Different demands were expressed in some Text+ User Stories, e.g. by Gabriel Viehauer (<https://www.text-plus.org/en/research-data/user-story-409/>), Manuel Braun (<https://www.text-plus.org/en/research-data/user-story-417/>), and Robert Langhanke (<https://www.text-plus.org/en/research-data/user-story-424/>).

³The DTABf shall stand as an example for the application of further common, simplifying customizations, such as TEI Lite.

⁴A more complex case, concerns the use of derived text formats from copyrighted text. Cf. Schöch et al. 2020.

⁵The FACT Principles (Fairness, Accuracy, Confidentiality, Transparency) address such responsibilities. Cf. Responsible Data Science (redasci.org).

of entities in resources, RDF allows statements about these entities and their relations. Consequently, BEACON can be regarded as a low-threshold precursor to RDF-based knowledge graphs.

Figure 1: GND-BEACON-Landscape by Harald Lordick 2022

The use of RDF in DSE is discussed widely,⁶ but has not become a commonly established practice yet.⁷ A big concern lies in the additional workload, if a project includes concepts of interoperability and accessibility beyond the scope of its own framework. Dumont 2019 suggests using RDF to produce semantic annotations, i.e. in DSE of letters, not only to identify entities such as people, places, and works, but to categorize them in describing their relations towards each other. Thus, relational information becomes machine-readable and accessible for different projects (Dumont 2019, 8, 17). The data is searchable through semantic queries, i.e. with SPARQL. The main challenge though lies in the development of one or more ontologies with a suitable vocabulary (Dröge 2010, 146) and the use of an appropriate annotation data model.

THE ROLE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS

The paper presents different approaches to interoperability of editions, highlighting their potentials, but also taking their limits and the associated efforts under consideration. Different levels of openness are addressed, as well as the distinct phases in which measures to open up editions can be integrated.

Current developments like the establishment of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) or the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) address demands of interoperability and connectivity – issues that have been around for quite some time, but now arise with greater urgency and scope. In the course of the activities in the NFDI-consortium Text+, previous work will be built upon, taken further, and complemented with new ideas

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Using IIF and Web Annotations to Publish TEI Editions

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INTRODUCTION

The KNAW Humanities Cluster, especially Huygens ING, has a long tradition of publishing digital scholarly editions⁸. Typically, these editions use custom annotation conventions and are published online using carefully designed custom web applications. Building these web apps is time consuming and expensive.

Current practices regarding digital editions were perceived inadequate for several reasons:

- Complex, detailed editing is often still done directly in TEI-XML.
- Editors often do not reuse each others' experience.
- Editions are not comparable.
- For many tasks technical support is necessary.
- Online publication is time consuming and requires extensive involvement of programmers.

Therefore, Huygens ING started eDITem ('a Digital Infrastructure for Edition Templates'). eDITem is a collaboration project between edition scholars and software developers with several objectives:

- Provide more autonomy and less dependency on software developers to editors.
- Introduce standardisation of editions by developing templates for a number of edition types.
- Build a software ecosystem for innovative online publication of digital scholarly editions.

TEI, LINKED OPEN DATA AND IIF

Editions at Huygens ING are grounded in a TEI-XML⁹ tradition. This has clear advantages (shared community practices, standardised format, wide range of application, etc) but also limitations (hierarchical structure, difficult to edit, semantically (too) rich, etc) (Bird 1999) (Bleeker et al. 2020). We want to retain our investments in TEI but at the same time overcome its limitations.

For many editions and other historic text collections Huygens ING cooperates with Cultural Heritage institutions. Examples are Mondrian and Van Gogh letter editions. Partner CH institutions like for example the Dutch Royal Library, National Archive, RKD Netherlands Institute for Art History, as well as NDE (Network Digital Heritage)¹⁰ want to publish their collections and databases as Linked Open Data¹¹. One important reason for this is that they want to contextualise their data sets. This contextualisation also applies to the scholarly editions we are publishing: our CH partners want meaningful links between our editions and their published data sets (e.g., RKD wants links to their artwork data for works discussed in Mondrian letters).

We as technicians at the KNAW Humanities Cluster support this Linked Open Data trend with our technical infrastructure solutions. Additionally, we are inspired by the linked data compliant approach of IIF (International Image Interoperability Framework)¹². This standard specifies how to publish image data online using two-dimensional numerical coordinates that are independent from the actual image formats that are used. It allows one to address, annotate or retrieve any part of an image using URLs containing such coordinates, independent of image format or quality.

Analogous to IIF we implemented a text service that supports addressing, annotation or retrieval of fragments of 'raw' (UTF-8) text with URLs containing numerical 'text coordinates'. Like IIF, we use Web Annotations¹³ to represent

⁸ <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/projecten/?thema=digitale-edities>

⁹ <https://tei-c.org/>

¹⁰ <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/>

¹¹ https://www.w3.org/egov/wiki/Linked_Open_Data

¹² <https://iif.io/>

¹³ W3C Web Annotations: <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>

annotations on our raw texts. We regularly discuss our work on this 'IIF for text' service with potential stakeholders, collect feedback and participate in ongoing international efforts¹⁴ to propose a standard for such a service.

Contrary to the self contained and highly structured TEI format we as technicians at the HuC take a rigorous standoff approach to text editions: we represent all edition information as raw text with standoff annotations on segments of this text.

TOOLS AND SERVICES

We built a processing pipeline that starts with TEI-XML documents that are typically created manually by editorial teams. We take this TEI apart, splitting it in raw (UTF-8) text plus standoff annotations, with no loss of information. All TEI structure and tagging is represented as separate layers of overlapping annotations on the text. Different types of annotations as determined by TEI elements are on separate parallel annotation layers.

For for example the Mondrian letter edition the text is split in words (tokenisation). We then use word indexes as coordinates to address text fragments ('the segment starting on word 12 and ending at word 22'). Text is stored in a repository¹⁵ and any fragment can be accessed using URLs of the following form:

```
https://{textrepo}/api/view/{doc-identifier}/segments/index/12/22
```

(Granularity of text coordinates is a project specific choice, could e.g. also be text lines or characters)

Annotations are represented as standard Web Annotations and stored in an Annotation Repository that we developed ourselves. AnnoRepo¹⁶ is a full implementation of the Web Annotation Protocol¹⁷, with extensions such as support for batch uploads, authentication and authorisation and searching for overlapping annotations.

The text and annotation repositories can be queried using web APIs to directly retrieve any data element, but can also provide data to interactive frontends that present scholarly editions online. We built a frontend¹⁸ that includes annotation based faceted search, a IIF image viewing component, 'IIF for text' text panels and panels that visualise annotations. This frontend is generic: it can be configured to search and visualise very different text collections: TEI editions, but also large historic text collections based on automatically transcribed large scan image archives.

EVALUATION

We want to retain our TEI workflows, but we gradually want to improve those by restricting ourselves to shared edition templates per edition type and by introducing new TEI and XML tools. We also built a processing pipeline that converts TEI to text plus annotations conforming to Linked Open Data standards. Our generic and configurable frontend can be used to easily visualise, browse and search (new versions of) online scholarly editions.

The LoD/IIF approach has several advantages over a TEI-only approach:

- It can easily be combined with other Linked Data sets such as those of our partner CH institutions, thus providing contextualisation.
- Editions are easily extendible with additional standoff annotation layers that can randomly overlap with existing annotations. This can even be done online and autonomously, by anybody with read only web access to the edition (Crane, 2018). Both we as edition providers and the scholars using our editions can in principle share the same annotation space published by the edition.
- Every detail of an edition is accessible online as data using URLs. Each part can be annotated or retrieved. Retrieved text can be used for the users' scholarly purposes, for example for automatic analysis or enrichment.
- Because of the fine-grained availability of edition text and annotations through web APIs it is easier to develop small, customised edition tools, or *micro-clients*.

¹⁴ <https://digitalscholarship.web.ox.ac.uk/article/unlocking-digital-texts>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/knaw-huc/textrepo>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/knaw-huc/annorepo>

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-protocol/>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/knaw-huc/textannoviz>

CONCLUSIONS

By introducing an alternative representation of digital scholarly editions as raw text plus standoff annotations we also introduced new ways to visualise, link, combine, annotate, enrich, and otherwise reuse edition data. Our vision is to change digital editions from online versions of books to semi-finished products: both edition data and edition tools and frontends should support change and extension: annotation layers and new micro clients or software components can be added by anybody, and at lost cost.

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Dynamic Data Life Cycle(s) on a Collaborative Edition Platform – from hallerNet to ch18Net

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This paper deals with the question of the use and reuse of digital scholarly editions including the related structural data. Starting from the examples of *hallerNet* and the emerging future *ch18Net* it reflects upon the applicability of classical concepts of data life cycles for collaborative edition platforms. The sequence of data life cycles relates to the collection, analysis, publication, and subsequent archiving as well as possible re-use of data. Hence, this perspective primarily focuses on the progression of individual projects with predefined objectives and durations. In contrast, collaborative platforms are characterised by a continuous enrichment and expansion of data. Although this process may be linked to projects, the emphasis is less on the conclusion but rather on the perpetual evolution. This approach requires a constant reflection on the existing concepts, an adaptation to current developments, and a differentiated set of instruments to ensure the quality and homogeneity of the data. A considerable challenge is to establish a financial and institutional foundation for the sustainability and advancement of the platform.

The platform *hallerNet* was developed from 2016 to 2019 when a large amount of structural data from two completed research projects, dating back to the early 1990s, has been converted from a relational database to an XML/TEI-based system. In the following project (2018-2023) supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation, 5,000 letters from Albrecht von Haller's correspondence and all his 9,800 reviews published in the «Göttingische Gelehrte Anzeigen» were edited. A central characteristic of the data-centric platform is the consistent linking of the structural data to digital scholarly editions via an elaborate reference system (Dängeli and Forney 2019). Currently, *hallerNet* comprises about 100'000 objects (e.g., persons, publications, institutions, places, or plants) which are not only internally but also externally linked in various ways via authority files (*GND*, *IdRef*, *VIAF*), *Metagrid*, *correspSearch*, *infoflora*, *geoNames*, and others. The *FAIR Data principles* form the foundation for the collection, processing, and availability of data (Dängeli and Stuber 2020). The existing environment enables the editing of different types of documents and their display in the frontend. It consists of the various components: a customized *Oxygen XML Editor* with forms and schema validation, a *SOLR*-powered search, an *IIIF Server* to deliver high-quality images, and a backend built on the open-source software *XSLWeb*. As crucial as the technical environment are conventions and the documentation tracked comfortably in Markdown (*Git* and *codiMD*).

Starting from the Bernese polymath Albrecht von Haller (1708-1777) as the central actor and eponym for the platform (Stuber, Hächler and Lienhard 2005), *hallerNet* currently strives for a Swiss-wide perspective to the emerging future platform *ch18Net*. The existing infrastructure is gradually expanded in collaboration with other platforms and projects at the universities Basel, Lausanne, and Neuchâtel, whose temporal focus is on the long 18th century. This common temporal and thematic emphasis of the collaborative platform is essential to ensure coherence. *hallerNet* and the future *ch18Net* make accessible knowledge networks in Switzerland in its European exchange during the transition from the *Republic of Letters* to the *Scientific Community*. The common focus results in sufficient overlap in the structural data of the different projects for the effort of homogenisation on the collaborative platform to be worthwhile. The continuous expansion increases the degree of interconnectedness within the platform, which opens new perspectives for research and analysis (Stuber and Krempel 2013; Sonntag, Stuber and Forney 2019; Stuber et al. 2022; Aeby, Heinzmann, Stuber [in print]). Concurrently, the existing data and data structures are perpetually adapted to new demands. Data is thus not merely accumulated but used, reused, and enriched in a dynamic and collaborative way. This process is not interrupted by time-consuming and resource-intensive exports and re-imports of data repositories.

The authors consider the described dynamic approach as an alternative method for the use and reuse of data in the context of digital scholarly editions. It differs from classical concepts of life data cycles, which are bound to project thinking. Especially for digital scholarly editions, there is a high demand for platforms that have a certain continuity on the one hand and meet the complexity of the research objects on the other. Accordingly, it is essential to articulate these needs to funding bodies to ensure a financially secure long-term operation of the platform. Institutional anchoring provides a vital foundation for such consolidation.

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One Edition – Multiple Interfaces. Dissemination and Preservation of Sustainable Digital Scholarly Editions

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INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we want to discuss three distinct phases in the life cycle of a digital scholarly edition (DSE): production, dissemination, and long-term storage. We will present our idea of a sustainable infrastructural model for DSEs, which includes the dissemination of one edition in multiple interfaces on various platforms.

The paper presents the strategies and ideas we are currently working to implement at Center for Grundtvig Studies, Aarhus University. The center hosts the meso-scaled project *Grundtvig's Works* (2009-2029) (www.grundtvigsvaerker.dk), which is the largest humanist project in terms of timeframe and funding on Danish ground so far. It is a critical edition of all works published by the Danish poet, pastor, politician, and romanticist N.F.S. Grundtvig (1783–1872), who is regarded as one of the most (if not the) central figure in the nineteenth-century Danish nation building process, as well as in the construction of a modern Danish Christianity. The project was envisioned by dedicated scholars and initiated by a consortium including members of the Danish parliament around 2008. The vision was a scholarly edited, digital version of Grundtvig's published writings, that should be available to Danish citizens free of charge. The writings, published within a period of 68 years (1804–1872), amount to 4M word tokens distributed over approximately 37K standard pages.

Managing a project like this impels the scholars to make their research results as widely available as possible. Our idea of a sustainable infrastructure is built around great openness of our data, and a tripartition of labour involved in making, rendering, and storing digital scholarly editions.

A SUSTAINABLE MODEL

DSEs are part of a now mature scholarly field in which methodologies, theories, and frameworks have been discussed and developed since the 1990ies, when digital became a standard prefix of the scholarly edition. Preservation and sustainability have always been an inherent concern for academics working on projects within Digital Humanities (Pitti 2004, Smith 2004). For producers of scholarly editions it is obvious that rendition and preservation should be considered two separate parts of the DSE (Turco 2016, Oltmanns et al. 2019). Thus, as scholarly editors we need to concern ourselves with the perils of long-term preservation and storage, as well as accessibility and renditions of the editions we produce. However, concerns and responsibilities are two different things. We would hold that responsibility for this is far too much to expect from scholars, and, indeed, not very sustainable. Rather, we envision a more firm tripartition of labour on a regional level that clearly divides responsibility for a) the production of the data, b) the short-term rendition of the given data sets, and c) for the long-term storage of data in a FAIR manner (figure 1, Baunvig et al. 2023).

Figure 1: The DSE Work Loop.

Every project will experience having to deal with a given material in need of processing by way of, e.g., OCR or Transkribus. The next step is the manual cleansing and mark-up of the given material carried-out by digital scholarly editors. The result hereof is what is rendered on given URLs for lay and scholarly users to consume; scholarly consumption of the DSE data can, however, also circumvent the rendition and focus alone on the 'raw' digitized material. The stage of storage is a separate endeavour. Here, no specific long-term model seems to have stabilized in the Nordic countries.

A tripartition of labour, as we suggest, is neither a bold nor a novel request. In fact, it has often been clearly stated that there is a need for independent infrastructure, for instance by Roberto Rosselli Del Turco: "We need a reliable third party, such as universities and other research institutions, offering support and preparing an adequate infrastructure for long-term publishing of select digital editions." (2016). However, this infrastructure still does not exist, at least not for projects within the Nordic region. We believe a solution for the long-term preservation and dissemination of scholarly editions in the Nordic countries would best exist on a regional level as we share many legislative, lingual, and funding characteristics.

FLOODING THE MARKET – MULTIPLE INTERFACES

Once funding runs out for a project, editors often have little or no saying as to the rendition of their editions. This, however, does not render interfaces obsolete; it just means they should not be considered permanent. It is true, as Tara L. Andrews and Joris J. van Zundert states, that "The interface is (...) an integral part of the argument that an edition makes about a text." (2018, 8). Thus, interfaces for rendition should be regarded a vital part of the edition, even though this part might not have a long durability. To ensure widely dissemination, and perhaps even longevity of the edition, we believe it is worth to flood the market. At Center for Grundtvig Studies, we are working on making our edition available in as many forms as possible, be it PDFs, e-books, and printed books. We will not make the whole oeuvre available in all forms, but make sure that the most influential out of the approx. 1000 works included in our edition are readily accessible to the public, who indirectly funded the project.

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Reusing and preserving research data: the example of grammateus

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INTRODUCTION

This presentation addresses the topic of long-term preservation of data through the prism of grammateus, a project in Digital Humanities at the University of Geneva which is preparing a Virtual Research Environment to study the typology of Greek Documentary papyri from ancient Egypt. This online environment offers new research data in the form of papyrological metadata and detailed descriptions of document types, but also relies on direct reuse of XML TEI files from databases such as the *Heidelberger Gesamtverzeichnis der Griechischen Papyrusurkunden Ägyptens* (HGV), and the *Duke Database of Documentary Papyri* (DDbDP) via the papyri.info website¹⁹.

The research results produced in the context of grammateus by the team, composed of three papyrologists and a specialist in Digital Humanities, must remain accessible and citable for future researchers, a challenge shared as well by digital editions. These results are potentially relevant over a long period of time – several decades, as is often the case in the Humanities, and particularly for scholarly editions.

In an academic context that does not fund the maintenance of digital projects such as grammateus over the (very) long term and given the inherent fragility of websites that depend not only on regularly updated external data, but also on constantly evolving web technologies, the question that arises is how to ensure long-term access to the scholarly output of digital projects?

For the grammateus project, we have chosen to focus on the preparation and archiving of quality data, following established standards. The typology of documentary papyri – everyday documents (letters contracts etc.) and non-literary documents – includes a description of each type along with an explanation of the classification process and a database of selected papyri illustrating the types of papyri. The data is therefore divided in two categories: on the one hand, there is the data relating to the papyri in the database, and on the other, the scholarly texts.

PAPYROLOGICAL DATABASE

The data relating to the papyri is partly produced by the team, but the transcriptions of documents in the database come from the *DDbDP* via *papyri.info*. Each papyrus is illustrated by a digital model that reproduces the text and adds a new layer of information: sections of text are highlighted in colour, as they play a role in the typology of the papyri. These models are updated each time the page is opened, so the data is dynamically integrated into grammateus. It should be noted that the community of papyrologists has developed a collaborative tool, the papyrological editor, which allows everyone to update the data on *papyri.info* - by adding new transcriptions, updating existing ones, or correcting metadata such as the date or provenance of a papyrus.

This dynamic access aspect of the project is an important innovation, as it demonstrates that it is possible to work with, and present, texts that are as up-to-date as possible, which is not usually the case. But on the other hand, dependence on papyri.info requires maintenance in order to preserve the functionality of grammateus: in addition to web technology changes such as the move to HTTPS, the standard EpiDoc encoding format (Eliott et al., 2007) for epigraphic texts or texts on papyrus, as well as the stylesheets (Eliott et al., 2008) that allow text to be converted to HTML format, are constantly evolving²⁰.

SCHOLARLY TEXTS

Textual data such as descriptions are also encoded in TEI, and are particularly sensitive to issues of access and durability. In fact, in order to take full advantage of online papyrological resources, grammateus will not result in a traditional publication in the form of a book printed by a publisher. The project's texts therefore face the same problems raised by Bleier (2021) for critical editions. Indeed, the typological descriptions can remain relevant over the very long term. For

¹⁹ <https://aquila.zaw.uni-heidelberg.de/start> (accessed 01.02.2023); <https://papyri.info/> (accessed 15.02.2023).

²⁰ The EpiDoc guidelines were updated to version 9.5 in April 2023. See <https://lsv.uky.edu/scripts/wa.exe?A2=MARKUP;53d0abb3.2304&S=> (accessed 14.07.2023).

example, scholarly texts dating from a century back or more are cited by the grammateus project: for instance, Wilcken (1912) is cited by Ferretti et al. (2023, §4). As well as presenting the archiving of data on Yareta, the University of Geneva's data repository, we will also discuss the issue of peer review for online resources: although it is an important aspect of validating a scholarly output, there is no obvious solution for grammateus.

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Max Frischs Notizen: eine neue digitale Edition unter einem grossen Dach

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ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Der Beitrag stellt die Digitale Edition der Notizen von Max Frisch vor. Neben der Präsentation des im Jahr 2022 gestarteten Projekts möchten wir insbesondere auf seinen institutionellen Kontext eingehen. Eine wichtige Besonderheit der Edition ist es, dass sie komplett unter dem Dach der ETH-Bibliothek realisiert wird. Die zu edierenden Handschriften stammen aus dem Bestand des Max Frisch-Archivs, das Teil der Sammlungen und Archive an der ETH-Bibliothek ist und in Kooperation mit der Max Frisch-Stiftung betrieben wird. Die Notizen werden innerhalb der Bibliothek digitalisiert, transkribiert, kommentiert, publiziert und archiviert. Dieses Setup ermöglicht eine dynamische und effiziente Realisierung, die gleichzeitig dazu anregt, die gelegentlich anzutreffende klare Differenzierung zwischen Gedächtnisinstitutionen, Forschung und Infrastruktur in unterschiedlicher Form zu hinterfragen.

DIE EDITION IM FORSCHUNGSKONTEXT

Die handschriftlichen Notizen des Schriftstellers, Architekten und ETH-Absolventen Max Frisch (1911-1991) verteilen sich auf mehr als 100 Notizhefte sowie mehrere Dutzend Notizblöcke, Ringordner und Zettelkonvolute. Sie sind grösstenteils unveröffentlicht und umfassen mehr als 6'000 Seiten. Die Notizen enthalten erste Entwürfe zu neuen Werken, sie zeigen den Schweizer Autor aber auch als aufmerksamen Beobachter des internationalen Zeitgeschehens, der durch das kriegszerstörte Europa reist, Japan, die Sowjetunion oder die USA erkundet. Neben Dialogen zu Theaterstücken, flüchtig notierten Prosa-Ideen und bereits ausformulierten Texten enthalten sie architektonische Skizzen, alltägliche Aufzeichnungen wie Telefonnummern und Adressen, ebenso Reflexionen zu wichtigen politischen Ereignissen und zu Begegnungen mit Personen der Zeitgeschichte (z. B. Henry Kissinger). Die Edition macht ein äusserst umfangreiches, bislang kaum zu überblickendes Textkorpus erstmals integral zugänglich. Aufgrund der Heterogenität und nicht-linearen Struktur des Materials erscheint eine digitale Edition, die unterschiedliche Zugänge ermöglicht, hierfür geradezu prädestiniert. Volltextsuche, Register, Verlinkungen und Kommentare bieten der Forschung künftig eine substantielle neue Quellengrundlage für textgenetische, biographische und literaturbetriebliche, aber auch zeit- und mentalitätsgeschichtliche Fragestellungen. Fachlich begleitet wird das Projekt von der Max Frisch-Stiftung sowie von der Professur für Literatur- und Kulturwissenschaft an der ETH Zürich.

BESCHREIBUNG DES WORKFLOWS

Für die Umsetzung der Edition wurde ein Workflow entwickelt, der in seinen Kernfunktionalitäten die heute gängigen Technologien verwendet: Der Erschliessungsprozess umfasst die Digitalisierung im DigiCenter der ETH-Bibliothek, die automatisierte Handschriftenerkennung mit Transkribus (inkl. einem eigenen Handschriftenmodell) sowie die TEI-XML-konforme Annotation und Kommentierung mit Hilfe des Oxygen-Editors. Als Plattform zur Präsentation des edierten Texts wird TEI Publisher eingesetzt und die Digitalisate werden dort via IIIF eingebunden. Die für die Edition entwickelten Transkriptions- und Annotationsrichtlinien orientieren sich zum grössten Teil am Basisformat des Deutschen Textarchivs (DTABf). Für die Erschliessung von Personen und Orten kann ein durch das Team der Fachstelle Digital Scholarship Services der Sammlungen und Archive der ETH-Bibliothek entwickeltes und auf Machine Learning basierendes Named Entity Recognition und Linking Verfahren genutzt werden, das durch die Annotationsfunktionalitäten in TEI Publisher ergänzt wird. Im Mittelpunkt steht hier die Verwendung von eindeutigen Identifikatoren wie der GND und darauf aufbauend die Vernetzung mit anderen Forschungsprojekten.

DIE EDITION ALS PILOTPROJEKT: PERSPEKTIVEN

In der Gesamtschau der unterschiedlichen Faktoren wird deutlich erkennbar, dass Gedächtnisinstitutionen in vielfacher Hinsicht zur Umsetzung eigener Editionen in der Lage sind. Im Idealfall verfügen sie über eigene Digitalisierungszentren, Hard- und Softwareressourcen sowie umfassende Erfahrung im langfristigen Betrieb von Services sowie in der Langzeitarchivierung. Im Kontext der Sammlungen und Archive der ETH-Bibliothek kommt ein

weiterer Aspekt hinzu, nämlich die gezielte Auseinandersetzung damit, wie Machine-Learning-Technologien für die Erschließung, Anreicherung und Vernetzung des bearbeiteten Materials genutzt werden können. Mindestens genauso wichtig ist jedoch, dass Gedächtnisinstitutionen in der Regel über eine Vielfalt an Beständen verfügen, die Editionsprojekte unterschiedlicher Grösse ermöglichen – von kleineren Projekten, beispielsweise im Rahmen von Lehrveranstaltungen, bis hin zu mehrjährigen Forschungsprojekten. Zudem sind die Mitarbeitenden der jeweiligen Gedächtnisinstitutionen in der Regel bestens – auch aus der Forschungsperspektive – mit dem Material vertraut. Diese Kombination aus Infrastruktur, innovativen Erschliessungstechnologien sowie der Motivation zur Erforschung und Präsentation des eigenen Materials ist zudem ein wichtiger Faktor für die Langzeitverfügbarkeit der auf diese Weise entstandenen Editionen, die als Teil der digitalen Bestandspflege verstanden werden können. Die in dieser Situation notwendige Konzentration auf die Bearbeitung eigener Bestände macht es wiederum notwendig, Möglichkeiten zu finden, wie Editionen miteinander vernetzt werden können – und zwar auch dann, wenn der Spielraum zur Nachnutzung der edierten Daten aus rechtlichen Gründen nur bedingt möglich ist. Weitgehend offen, insbesondere auch im Umfeld von Gedächtnisinstitutionen, bleibt zudem, wie diese zusätzlichen Aufgaben finanziell gefördert werden können.

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DSE meets Library – The *Basler Edition der Bernoulli-Briefwechsel (BEBB)* and the University of Basel Library in reciprocal long-term collaborative Settings, and beyond

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INTRODUCTION

Opening up of a DSE²¹ proves to be advantageously done through close cooperation with the library sector. We show, using the example of the *Basler Edition der Bernoulli-Briefwechsel (BEBB)*, how the long-standing collaboration with the library spanning from the era of physical resources to the digital present, yielded mutual benefits for the edition, the library, its users and the researchers who consult both the edition and the library catalogues and resources. We point out the interconnected history of the edition and the library, indicate the technologies and methods involved, and give a short evaluation of the editorial settings and lastly sketch some promising scenarios for the future for DSEs and libraries, i.e. the expanding of the cooperation in the direction of digital infrastructure library services, thereby supporting the editorial scholarly community, not only with printed material, ebooks and e-journals but also sustainable editorial research environments (eVRE).

BEBB digital meets Library

The digital concept of the *Basler Edition der Bernoulli-Briefwechsel BEBB* was right in the beginning shaped by the cooperation with the University Library of Basel (UB). The first step in the transformation from a print to a digital edition was the compilation and collection of the metadata of all known Bernoulli letters – even of the non extant-ones – in a database and later an online inventory, the *Basler Inventar der Bernoulli-Briefwechsel BIBB*, 1997-2003, consisting of more than 5,000 letters²². The collected metadata was integrated into the catalogue of the manuscript section of the local university library (UB) – the respective catalogued records being at the time part of HAN (Dill 2018). This specialised catalogue was then being rebuilt and the data ingested in 2011 into the now commonly used Swisscollections catalogue using exclusively open source modules²³. Swisscollections can best be described as a metacatalogue of holdings in special library and archival collections in Switzerland, of which the Letters of the eminent mathematicians and natural philosophers Bernoulli are one special collection of more than 500,000 archival items overall. New features are e.g. so-called deep links with which fields can be queried apart from the filters or fields of the search interface.

The opening up of the Bernoulli edition *towards the library* brought clear benefits. The edition's (meta)data is for instance linked to other central platforms such as e-manuscripta or Kalliope and GND. Swisscollections draws the data at least partially from the larger Swiss library ecosystem SLSP and therefore is also searchable there. The BEBB gets also a better long-term perspective through the continuous and long-standing maintenance of data and through the furthering of the access to digital collections and their metadata, and the securing of availability and (re)usability for purposes of the researchers, or the use of the general public. This is ensured by the UB Digital Library strategic directions and their longtime perspective (Strategie 2021). The BEBB operates in an environment of a centuries-old cultural heritage institution which has been and still is responsible for the maintenance of the Swisscollections catalogue, now for more than 10 years. Special search functionalities were developed for BEBB by the UB IT Department in cooperation with the editorial team.

For the library (UB Basel), the opening *towards the edition* also brings benefits. The aim of the edition and the online cataloguing is very similar: opening up of information through descriptive evaluation and enhancing discoverability of sources in a more research-driven manner for the scholarly community. This is especially the case with the Bernoulli inventory which formed the basis for the re-cataloguing of the library's own manuscript holdings. The BIBB inventory

²¹Digital Scholarly Edition

²²<https://ub-mediawiki.unibas.ch/bernoulli/index.php/Quellenmaterial>

²³<https://swisscollections.ch/Bibliographien/BibliographiesSpecial#>;

was made by science historians with profound expertise in the subjects treated in the letters. This deep knowledge became as far as possible part of the library catalogue. Every new research result that has an impact on the metadata is integrated and ingested into the catalogue system. On the other hand, the required transformation of the Bernoulli Letters Inventory as a central part of the edition, and of Swisscollections, also entails some limitations and challenges, such as the difficulty of accommodating the edition metadata in a system designed to the specific needs of a library catalogue aimed above all at discoverability and identifiability of holdings in the libraries. Quite a challenge in the latter phase of the digital edition project was the integration through a Python-scripted exporting process of the BIBB inventory records, which are coded and structured according to the MARC21 library standard with its strict field assignments, into TEI XML for eXistdb/TEI Publisher based BEBB^{digital}.

We conclude that in all phases, from the print-only to Media Wiki to the TEI-XML edition by means of the toolbox TEI Publisher the support of the library was essential and an integral partner of the successive Bernoulli projects with benefits on both sides. The technical, infrastructural and data specific challenges could be solved successfully and sustainably, in particular because of the close cooperation and the merging of the respective expertise in an institutional symbiosis.

Apart from library cooperative approaches and also the much needed hosting services, preferably by the library IT, we see further potential for future developments through applying Linked Open Data, NLP, or graph based and metadata aggregating approaches (Hotson, Wallnig 2019; EMLO)²⁴. Deepening the data structures may be achieved by applying e.g. historicized geo-referencing (HISTOGIS). But above all BEBB-UB-cooperation may serve as a paradigmatic model for DSEs, both institutions together building a physical and virtual research infrastructure (Leblanc 2018, Bögel 2013) – reinforced by essential stakeholders: the Academy (SAGW), the Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities, the University and its Research Support unit, and e-editions.

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²⁴ <http://emlo.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/>, which is also based in the local university library (Bodleian) – and the Oxford Humanities Division.

Modelling, Visualising and Preserving Intermediality: Annemarie Schwarzenbach's Letters, Photographs and Small Forms ('Kleine Formen')

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Although the Swiss writer, photographer, and traveljournalist Annemarie Schwarzenbach (1908-1942) is one of the most famous and most researched female Swiss authors (Obermüller 2008), her work has so far only been available in fragments and hardly true to the text, let alone in scholarly editions (Fähnders/Rohlf 2005, Decock/Schaffers 2014). The project plans to fulfil this desideratum for 75% of her writings, namely the author's letters, which have hardly been accessible up to now, as well as the scattered (photographic) reports, feuilletons, stories and reviews (summarised as small forms/Kleine Formen). In addition, Annemarie Schwarzenbach's photographs, which have already been published digitally, will be integrated. Until now, these have largely been analysed separately from the written work. The photographs have been presented on the digital map *Am Ende aller Wege* (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft 2020, Wagner 2021), that shall be expanded towards an intermedial presentation (see below). Schwarzenbach created texts and photographs interdependently on her journeys (Wichor 2008), in her own words she produced 'paper flags on an imaginary map' (Schwarzenbach 1940). Research has built on this mention and pointed out that the oeuvre creates its own 'tempo- and topographies' (Decock 2010). The project aims to make these spaces of Annemarie Schwarzenbach's intermedial work accessible for the first time.

Provided a successful grant application, the project will begin in summer 2024 with a duration of four years. This paper is not intended as a presentation of a completed design process but would like to invite the community to participate in it. It focuses on the challenges of modelling, visualising, and preserving our intermedial data. Many projects face this kind of challenges (e.g. "the critical hybrid edition" *Der ganze Schwitters*, Forschungsstelle/Archiv Kurt Schwitters 2023, Schulz 2016; or Nutt-Kofoth 2019), and they require differentiated approaches that are appropriate to the specific subject matter (Sahle 2013, 181).

1. Modelling: The edition is based on printed texts with and without photographs (e.g., newspaper reports and photo reportages), on typescripts with and without handwritten annotations, on manuscripts of varying legibility as well as on stand-alone photographs and photographs on index cards with handwritten annotations. While these very heterogeneous sources may all be processed as image digitisations in a first step, their subsequent modelling in a searchable data structure is characterised by renewed differentiation in their TEI-XML markup. A challenge lies in the integration of the photographs. If they directly relate to the text (in the case of the photo reports or the index cards), their topography is marked up in relation to the text's topography. If photographs are explicitly or implicitly referred to in the text, they appear in the form of a reference, which may be rendered for instance as a modal in the graphical interface. Conversely, the photographs may also be marked up in such a way that texts to which they refer are listed in their metadata (either embedded in EXIF/XMP metadata or in a sidecar file). Schwarzenbach's texts and photographs thus become comprehensible in their intermediality, i.e. in their mutual media-specific dependence.

2. Visualisation: On the one hand, the encoded data will be made accessible in the 'classical way' by browsing, search functions and registers. On the other hand, the project will offer three spatio-temporal visualisation tools that do justice to the 'imaginary landscape' of Schwarzenbach's intermedial work. Topographically, the visualisation entails a world map on which all the places referenced in the (meta-)data of text or photography are localised. It is based on the web application *Am Ende aller Wege*, enriching it with texts and adding Annemarie Schwarzenbach's complete travel routes. The entities on the map may be filtered e.g. by time, media lity or correspondence functions (dispatch/reception). To better exploit the social aspects of Schwarzenbach's communication, an interactive network visualisation will allow to identify and arrange correspondence partners around Schwarzenbach according to various criteria; if the correspondence contains explicit or implicit references to photographs or if photographs were sent together with the letters, this will also be apparent. These visualisations are complemented by a *timeline* supplemented by biographical events, which visualises works and genres chronologically and allows various media categories to be shown or hidden.

3. Preserving: The challenges of preserving an intermedial edition are not fundamentally different from other edition projects and they are best handled using a layered approach. Whereas the preservation on the level of data is mainly a matter of best practices, keeping web applications alive is more difficult. A cornerstone of the data preservation is the sensible handling of research data (suitable formats, completeness and comprehensibility, versioning, attention to FAIR criteria). A large part of the image data is already secured by memory institutions, as the project can draw on the digitised photographs (HelveticArchives, E-Manuscripta and Wikimedia) as well as various digitised newspaper volumes of major Swiss newspapers or magazines (e-periodica.ch and e-newspaperarchives.ch) by way of the IIIF APIs. The project's own digitised material will be stored on a IIIF server at the University Library of Bern and might subsequently be transferred to the above-mentioned institutions (negotiations pending). The presentation of the digital edition is decoupled from the image data storage. Its architectural choice is targeted towards long term maintainability and availability (using modularity, loose-coupling, priority of static assets). Transforming the TEI based data in a pipeline-based fashion allows for future corrections and extensions. In addition to this, the project data will be ingested into the graph-based infrastructure of the DaSCH Basel (based on a light-weight ontology). This will allow for interoperability with other DaSCH datasets, but on a functionally reduced level. Lastly, the data will also be stored in archival formats on suitable platforms such as OLOS or Zenodo. Combining these strategies, the project's focus on intermediality will hopefully be preserved in the long term without functional impediments.

By showing the steps from data modelling and mediation to preservation, we hope to engage the research community in a fruitful discussion about digital editing of intermedial data.

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A Long Way for a Short Link: Insights into the Transformation of the Anton Webern Gesamtausgabe from a Print-only to a Hybrid Edition

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INTRODUCTION

Originally conceived as a traditional print edition, the Anton Webern Gesamtausgabe (AWG) has travelled a long road with a lot of detours to articulate its innovative approach to digital music edition, which still is struggling with issues of the editorial object, the technical realization of ideas, and the needed infrastructure. The proposed paper aims to outline this transformation process and critically discuss challenges and lessons learned.

STAGE 1: PRINT EDITION SUPPORTED BY DIGITAL TOOLS

The project of the AWG started back in 2006 with a funding by the SNSF for the preparation of a traditional printed musical edition of the works of Austrian composer Anton Webern (1883–1945). While the focus of this print-only edition was on gathering and organizing the necessary textual and musical materials, and preparing them for physical publication, challenges emerged when dealing with the edition of sketches whose original format would have barely fit into standard print formats. Ideas were loosely discussed to publish the sketches in digital form (whatever that meant around 2010). Concurrently, contextual materials and digital copies were organized using a Filemaker instance and later transferred to the SALSAH database developed at that time by the DHLab at the University of Basel.

STAGE 2: TRANSITION FROM PDF TO SALSAH [TO NIE-INE] TO DASCH

The project encountered a first major shift when changes in the SNSF's funding conditions in the early 2010's rendered the initial print-only concept no longer viable. Initial ideas on linking various edition contents were captured in a PDF format (Anton Webern Gesamtausgabe 2015). The transformation from this static PDF to a more dynamic digital environment included multiple steps: Firstly, the experience gained from working the contextual materials and digital copies in SALSAH provided the opportunity to envision integrating other components of the edition (like transcriptions, critical reports) into such a virtual research environment, offering enhanced organization, interlinking, and accessibility of edition-related data and information (Schingnitz and Schweizer 2016). Secondly, in addition to the actual database, a web application prototype "awg-app" (Anton Webern Gesamtausgabe 2016–2023) was developed internally to experiment with ideas such as displaying edited musical texts as SVG graphics and enriching them with additional data to enable various functionalities such as links to critical commentary. (While considered multiple times, a comprehensive encoding of the musical texts in, e.g., the format of the Music Encoding Initiative, MEI, was not deemed suitable at the time.)

These methodological and technological advancements were accompanied by institutional changes, most notably the establishment of NIE-INE in 2016. The AWG was fortunate to become one of the project partners during this time, fostering hopes and expectations for future collaboration and support in terms of a comprehensive edition infrastructure. However, the discontinuation of NIE-INE in 2019 also meant an enormous setback and infrastructural gap for the associated edition projects.

With the institutionalization of the Swiss National Data and Service Center for the Humanities (DaSCH) in 2017, the AWG gained another project partner dedicated to the long-term sustainability and accessibility of project data. With the support of DaSCH, the SALSAH database of the AWG was finally migrated to the DaSCH Service Platform (DSP) in 2023 ensuring the preservation and availability of the AWG's digital resources. Further development is still required to implement the solutions developed for the awg-app into DSP.

STAGE 3: THE VISION OF A LINKED/SEMANTIC SCHOLARLY MUSICAL EDITION

Another conceptual shift happened in parallel to the developments described in Stage 2. The graph-oriented data modelling of the SALSAH database (while using SQL in the back), the ontologies and graph models developed by NIE-

INE, and the RDF-based approach used by DaSCH, among others, triggered and reinforced the idea of applying a graph-based approach to the organization of edition content as well, opening visions of the edition as a linked data hub in the realm of semantic web. These visions include two main aspects in particular. First, the use of defined ontologies as a structural tool for the organization, storage, and searchability of the entire edition in a machine-readable format (Münnich 2018; Münnich 2019). Second, the presentation of detailed insights into the chronological and/or compositional genesis of sketches or musical texts. The awg-app explores these ideas by employing RDF graph models representing the current set of sketches. The underlying RDF data, accessed via the SPARQL query language, allow users to view, filter, and refine the edition. By embracing those principles of linked data and semantic web technologies, the AWG aims to create a scholarly musical edition that not only presents the edition content in a comprehensive and interconnected manner but also enables researchers to delve into detailed aspects of the composition process. This approach enhances the scholarly value and accessibility of the edition, offering new perspectives and avenues for exploration in the study of Anton Webern's compositions (Münnich and Ahrend 2021).

FUTURE CHALLENGES

The challenges that arise from such “open-heart surgery”, i.e. the continuous development of the digital concept of an edition during ongoing operations, are manifold: First, the digital and physical concepts and components of the edition must be permanently coordinated and kept up to date. Second, it is necessary to react flexibly to changing (infra-)structural conditions, which may also involve technological changes, while not losing sight of one's own long-term needs and ideas with respect to fundamental philological objectives of the project. (This is all the more true as the AWG is one of the few musical editions in the Swiss research landscape.) This also touches on the question of the status of edition projects as either mere data providers or knowledge creators in their own right in the humanities. Ongoing technological challenges for the AWG include the long-term maintenance and preservation of the tools developed as part of the project, including the prototype app, embedding and storing SVG (XML) files in DSP, and converting artificially generated RDF structures into real-world Linked Data.

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Creating and Curating Corpora of Annotated Music Scores for Distant Listening

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INTRODUCTION

This paper discusses the collection and curation of research data in the context of the SNSF-funded project “Distant Listening – The Development of Harmony over Three Centuries (1700–2000)”, carried out at EPFL’s Digital and Cognitive Musicology Lab (DCML). The data consists of digital editions of composed and transcribed music with additional annotations of latent musical phenomena such as key, harmony, phrase, cadence, or overall form (for instance, Hentschel, Neuwirth, and Rohrmeier 2021). We present the well-documented corpus creation pipeline originating from the project, which has served as guideline for the creation of one of the largest collections of annotated music scores available to date. The first part of the presentation focuses on the underlying convictions, decisions and design choices regarding the involved formats, infrastructures, and workflows. The second part represents a critical evaluation of the curation architecture, discussing key aspects such as FAIRness and data longevity, and highlighting some insights and lessons learned that will inform our future efforts and, potentially, other projects and contexts.

THE DISTANT LISTENING CORPUS

The Distant Listening Corpus (to be submitted for publication later in 2023) is organized in self-contained data repositories each of which forms a corpus representative of a particular musical style (London 2013) and, thanks to Git version control (e.g., Swicegood 2008), brings along the track record of its genealogy. It consists of music scores in the XML format of the free and open-source score editor MuseScore 3 (.mscx) which represent symbolic encodings of the print editions delivered alongside in PDF format. The documentation of the corpus creation pipeline lays out the details of how particular elements are to be encoded and have served our collaborators who either typeset the scores from scratch or converted and adapted scores that were freely available on the web. We touch upon the difficult trade-off, and its repercussions, between a full-fledged digital scholarly edition on the one hand (for which the MEI format (Roland 2002; Hankinson, Roland, and Fujinaga 2011), arguably, would be the better fit), and scores as “mere” research data in the sense of a structured representation of (only) those objects that are of interest.

THE CORPUS CREATION PIPELINE

The largest section of the documentation concerns the annotation part of the pipeline, which involves music theory experts who have been trained in using the DCML harmony annotation syntax. The workflow uses automatization features on the GitHub platform to validate both scores and annotations against the standards laid out in the documentation. Furthermore, it involves a round of review by another expert and the discussions leading up to consensus are an insightful resource themselves (the annotation workflow has been described in more detail in Hentschel et al. 2021). Although the fact that the deliberations on different analytical viewpoints are accessible to the users of the dataset is certainly an asset, their being stored on the GitHub platform exclusively is among the architecture’s weak points when it comes to longevity and FAIRness and solicits practical solutions for their conservation.

DISSEMINATION AND METADATA

The last part of the pipeline is concerned with finalizing a corpus and preparing it for publication. This includes harmonizing the directory structure, cleaning and adding metadata, adding URIs to identify data, as well as building and including a documentation homepage containing interactive figures summarizing and analyzing the data. Since our scores are self-contained in the sense that, apart from the score elements themselves, they contain all metadata and annotation labels originating from our curation efforts, we also discuss the technical tools developed at the DCML that can facilitate the above-mentioned tasks through batch editing. Our pipeline documentation tries to reflect and combine best practices from musicology (e.g., naming conventions), librarianship (e.g., norm data), and semantic web technologies (e.g., Wikidata identifiers). We present it in the hope that it can help disseminate some of these best practices and welcome suggestions for further improvement.

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FAIR tools for digital music critical editions

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Music scores are a particular type of textual document. They use music notation, rather than alpha-numeric symbols, as a system, that has evolved constantly over centuries, to represent and transmit sound. This constant evolution has been driven by the need for composers to express and share with musicians new musical ideas, and, in the process, they invent new symbols or new ways to interpret existing symbols. As a result, many types of music notation systems exist. In Western culture, music notation documents are most often written in Common Western Music Notation (CWMN), also known as standard notation or staff notation, which is the system used to represent musical pitch, rhythm, and other performance related musical elements in Western classical music. This system remained structurally consistent between approximately 1600 to 1900.

Creating digital editions for music requires addressing the structural particularities of music notation. This yields a range of challenges, from defining the appropriate way to represent the symbolic notation digitally, to having tools and workflows in place for creating and publishing the data. The particularities of music notation documents were the reason for Perry Roland to start, in 2002, the Music Encoding Initiative (MEI), a project inspired by the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI). MEI follows TEI in adopting XML, and the current schema of MEI is defined using the TEI “One Document Does-it-all” (ODD) tooling. While MEI initially focused primarily on CWMN, its modular structure has allowed for other types of music notations to be represented in markup, such as Renaissance mensural music notation, medieval neume notation, or tablature notation for plucked string instruments. Over the years, MEI has become the most widely used encoding scheme for digital critical editions of music. It is also used in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) applications, in music analysis, and in music visualization or performance related applications.

For some years, the absence of dedicated tools was a significant problem for the MEI community, and workarounds had to be found for converting data to and from other encoding systems for which tools for data input and rendering were available. Working with digital music editions is not really feasible using only standard XML tools, since the complex multi-dimensional structure of music notation does not always follow the strictly hierarchical format of XML. The complexity of the encodings also means that encoding MEI documents by hand is not scalable, and the resulting XML encoded documents still need to be transformed into rendered music notation. That meant the full expressiveness of the MEI schema could not be fully utilized and many of the unique encoding features of MEI were not available to projects. Over time, however, contributors within the MEI community have developed dedicated tools and have put in place different solutions for working with MEI data.

The RISM Digital Center is one of these contributors, starting in 2014 with the development of Verovio, an open-source software library for engraving music scores encoded in MEI. It is a flexible tool that can be used in a wide range of applications. Projects use Verovio in the context of digital critical editions, genetic editions, early music, audio alignment, online editing, music addressability, visualization, performance, and even composition via artificial intelligence. One of the unique features of Verovio is that it renders music notation into SVG while preserving the original structure of the MEI, including element XML IDs and element names through corresponding SVG class names. Verovio features a set of methods for retrieving information about MEI elements in the rendering context, including time-related information in MIDI sound files—another output format that Verovio can produce. This design allows SVG music notation to serve as an interaction layer for building dynamic applications in several computing contexts, including web applications, mobile apps, and server-side processing tools.

With the advent of Verovio and other tools for MEI, the RISM Digital Center has wholeheartedly embraced its role as a research infrastructure. This entails both the development and maintenance of tools for research projects as well as extending their utility beyond these endeavors. In this paper, we will explore the crucial decisions made during the ten years of development and how they have shaped a strategy that aligns with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, as applied to tools and research infrastructure. Furthermore, we will delve into how the unique characteristics of the domain necessitated a strong emphasis on interoperability and reusability. Designing tools with a focus on reusability encourages the sharing and repurposing of resources, empowering researchers to build upon existing

work. This approach accelerates progress and cultivates a sense of collective knowledge advancement within the musicological community.

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Augmentation of the Panorama of the Battle of Murten (1893): an Experimental Annotation System for the World Largest Digital Image of a Single Object

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DIGITAL SCHOLARLY EDITION OF RICH VISUAL MATERIAL

The subject of Scholarly Edition and Digital Scholarly Edition has predominantly revolved around text-based content, and this phenomenon can be attributed to historical and technical reasons. Throughout history, the inclusion of visual material in books has been prohibitively expensive, even with the advent of printing technology. Additionally, the annotation of visual material in books, especially when it is large and of an unusual format, is constrained by various factors such as page size, aspect ratio, reader's reading habits, typesetting, and printing quality. However, digital tools allow us to reimagine how we approach this challenge. Patrick Sahle defined Digital Scholarly Editions as “scholarly editions that are guided by a digital paradigm” (Sahle 2016, 28) and emphasized the need for researchers to expand scholarly editing beyond “literary texts” to “cover all cultural artefacts from the past” (Sahle 2016, 22). This new approach has been exemplified in various domains, such as film — *Documenting the digital edition on film* (Martinez 2017) — and virtual world — *3D Scholarly Editions for Byzantine studies* (Higuchi, R., and K. Murata. 2023). Taking advantage of recent advancements in digital imaging, streaming technology, and virtual annotation, this paper aims to propose a novel form of Digital Scholarly Edition that incorporates a rich visual material from cultural heritage²⁵.

Led by the Laboratory for Experimental Museology (eM+) and in partnership with the Murten Panorama Foundation, Digitising and Augmenting the Panorama of the Battle of Murten (DIAGRAM) aims to create an ultra-high resolution digital twin of the Panorama of the Battle of Murten (1893) by Louis Braun (1836-1916), the renowned German panorama painter. Depicting the Battle of Murten (1476), the panorama commemorates the Swiss victory against the Duchy of Burgundy in 1476 and is regarded as the national icon that defined the Swiss identity. The goal of the augmentation component is to augment content for both scholarly and public audience using a unified annotation backend.

WORLD LARGEST DATASET OF A SINGLE OBJECT

The panorama measures approximately 10 x 100 metres. Sampling at 1,000 dpi, the digital twin is anticipated to be a 1.6 Terapixels and 9.6 Terabytes single image. The content encapsulated within the panorama is remarkably dense, encompassing a myriad of elements. Among these includes a minimum of 20 named geographical locations, a minimum of 12 historical characters, 142 heraldic representations, a minimum of 23 recognized historical events, thousands of soldiers portrayed in various armaments and actions, and civilian bystanders in various costumes.

Technology advancement have facilitated the realization of annotations of large-scale rich visual material. First, billion-pixel imaging captures details which goes beyond human visual acuity. Second, streaming technology such as pyramid tile enables viewers to seamlessly explore any section of the terapixel image in real-time. Third, International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) Presentation API provides a virtual environment for researchers to produce and disseminate searchable annotation on the panorama at any zoom-level, transcending the limitation of fixed size inherent in printing publications.

²⁵ Some example projects. Foys, Martin K. 2003. *The Bayeux Tapestry Digital Edition*. Leicester: Scholarly Digital. <http://sd-editions.com:9090/bayeux/baytext.htm>. Quintman, Andrew, and Kurtis R. Schaeffer. 2021. “Synthesizing Image and Text in the Life of the Buddha.” *Digital Humanities and Research Methods in Religious Studies: An Introduction*, 97. Luo, Xiaoxi, Xu Tan, and Xiaoguang Wang. 2019. “Semantically Enriched Presentation for Cultural Heritage Image: A POI-Based Perspective.” In *2019 ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL)*, 410–11. Champaign, IL, USA: IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JCDL.2019.00094>. Wang, Xiaoguang, Ningyuan Song, Xuemei Liu, and Lei Xu. 2021. “Data Modeling and Evaluation of Deep Semantic Annotation for Cultural Heritage Images.” *Journal of Documentation* 77 (4): 906–25. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-06-2020-0102>.

SEMANTIC ANNOTATION

Our scholarly editing approach is founded on the identification and marking points of interest (POIs) in the panorama. These POIs are subsequently described using linked data controlled vocabulary and semantic annotation. Selected POIs of public interest will be augmented with additional media, such as 3D models, volumetric videos, ambisonics, and high-resolution gigapixel images and exhibited in museum context on eM⁺'s state-of-the-arts visualization systems.

The panorama encompasses a diverse range of subjects that invite cross-domain annotation from various fields, including medieval studies, military history, fashion history, heraldic studies, human geography, architectural history, and art history. To facilitate this comprehensive annotation process, three key steps will be undertaken to establish a functional annotation system. Firstly, selection and examination of controlled vocabularies and taxonomies from the different domains are required. Secondly, an extension to the existing IIIF annotation model is necessary. Currently, vanilla IIIF annotation only supports tagging via URIs and free-text commenting. Within the field of art history, there is a strong interest in adding a semantic qualifier to IIIF tagging to differentiate between instantiation (`rdfs:type`), equivalence (`owl:sameAs`), subject (`dc:subject`), copy from (`schema:isBasedOn`), and many other nuanced relations (Clarke 2015; Loh 2017; Bojars, Rasmane, and Zogla 2017). Thirdly, to enable multilingual search capabilities, a cross-domain ontology is needed to facilitate the enrichment and storage of data in a triplestore or a search engine backend.

The battle of Murten possesses a critical history of its own and has accumulated an archive. Thanks to the research conducted by the restoration team of the panorama in 1999, and our recent contributions, the archive now consists of a rich assemblage of preparatory drawings and iconographical source materials, two previous illustrations of the battle of Murten (one etching on copper and one on parchment), conference proceedings, and most notably, a 670-page edition of archival documents related to the battle²⁶, which may have served as both textual and visual inspiration for the panorama. We aspire to develop our annotation system to support the linking of the POIs and the content of the archive. In art history, tracking of visual lineage assumes a fundamental role in the iconographical analysis. Thus, we can view a comprehensive iconographical annotation map as the scholarly edition of rich visual materials. Again, this endeavour necessitates the utilization of appropriate taxonomies that describe the (art)-historical scholarly domain²⁷.

SUPPLEMENTARY SCHOLARLY EDITION

The augmentation project also involves a scholarly edition of *Die Urkunden der Belagerung und Schlacht von Murten*. As the text is transcribed and printed, it should be relatively straightforward for OCR process. However, as the documents are written in Old French, Old German, and Latin, the process of named entity recognition within them presents challenges.

CONCLUSION

In summary, this paper proposes a digital scholarly edition that addresses rich visual materials. By leveraging advanced imaging techniques, semantic annotation, and scholarly domain modelling, the project aims to enhance our understanding with the Panorama of the Battle of Murten and will result in a series of interactive and immersive museum installations, as well as a scholarly interface geared towards researchers in digital humanities.

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²⁷ Example projects extending IIIF annotation with general scholarly taxonomies. Frisch, Nicholas. 2020. "Primary Sourcing: The Ten Thousand Rooms Platform for Digital Annotation of Primary Source Images." *Journal of Chinese History* 4 (2): 536–43. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jch.2020.25>. Shu-Jiun Chen. 2021. "Design of Interoperability in Digital Humanities: A Case Study of the Interpretation and Restoration of the Han Dynasty Wooden Slips From Edsen-Gol." *Journal of Educational Media & Library Sciences* 58 (2): 193–235. [https://doi.org/10.6120/JoEMLS.202107_58\(2\).0007.RS.AM](https://doi.org/10.6120/JoEMLS.202107_58(2).0007.RS.AM). Laan, Bauke van der, Sofie Veramme, Evelien Hauwaerts, Joly Van Malderen, Katrien Deroo, Sarah Eloy, and Hendrik Defoort. n.d. "Annotation Demo Showcasing the Liber Floridus." Mmmonk. Accessed June 27, 2023. <https://www.mmmmonk.be/en/about-iiif/iiif-demo-liber-floridus>.

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The Munch and Ibsen Digital Scholarly Editions: Connecting works, life, and art

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INTRODUCTION

Digital scholarly editions (DSEs) (Sahle 2016) have transformed the way we engage with literary works, providing enhanced accessibility, interactivity, and depth of analysis. Despite their advantages, DSEs often remain disconnected from relevant content related to the artist. This paper is based on the ongoing work with the DSEs of two prominent Norwegians, the artist Edvard Munch, and the playwright Henrik Ibsen. How can these editions be supplied with external content to enrich scholarly research, foster interdisciplinary exploration, and facilitate a holistic understanding of each artist's work within their historical and cultural context?

Edvard Munch (1863–1944) and Henrik Ibsen (1828–1906) are key figures in Norway's cultural export and crucial to Norwegian identity and cultural heritage. Hence, they have been the objects of several research and documentation projects, and the transition to digital formats in galleries, libraries, archives, and museums has contributed to the vast amount of digital material on them: manuscripts, artworks, theater productions, cultural networks, correspondences, bibliographies, databases, reviews, translations and diverse archival material.

eMunch.no – digitalt arkiv

Digitallisering Museets prosjektgruppe arbeider med digitalisering av korrespondansen til Edvard Munch samt med ferdigstilling av Munchs egne tekster. Materialet korrekturettes og kodes for det publiseres her. Alle registrerte avsendere (med lister over brevene de sendte til Munch) og omtalte personer og institusjoner blir etter hvert tilgjengelig her i det digitale arkivet.

Gi oss gjerne [tilbakemelding!](#) [Les mer om nettstedet](#) | [Munch auf Deutsch](#) | [Munch en français](#) | [The English edition](#)

English edition of a selection of Munch's texts

The edition is a collaboration between translator Francesca M. Nichols and members of the museum's staff. The 68 selected texts contain essential art-related notes and many of Munch's literary sketches and prose poems, some in multiple versions. We have made an effort to remain true to Munch's authentic style of writing and present the translations side-by-side with facsimiles of the originals. – We would appreciate any [feedback](#) you might like to contribute. Be sure to follow us as new material and new functions become available. Go to [the English edition](#)

«- Jeg havde kanskje tjent kunsten og mit land mer hvis jeg var blevet boende i Paris - nå»

EDVARD MUNCHS TEKSTER # MM.N.2898

Figure 1: Screenprint of Edvard Munch's writings

THE DSEs AND EVERYTHING ELSE

Munch is primarily known as a visual artist, but left behind a collection of manuscripts and letters. Ibsen on the other hand was primarily a playwright, but aspired to be a painter in his younger days and created several paintings and drawings. Their writings and letters have been carefully digitized, transcribed, xml-encoded and edited, and made available as DSEs^{28,29} (See Figure 1, Figure 2). Their artworks are available on separate media platforms^{30,31} (See Figure 3, Figure 4), and

²⁸ <https://emunch.no/>

²⁹ <https://ibsen.uio.no/>

³⁰ <https://www.munchmuseet.no/en/edvard-munchs-artworks>

³¹ <https://ibsenstage.hf.uio.no/arkiv/eng/IbsenArts/IbsenArt>

bibliographical information is available in the online library catalogue³² and the International Ibsen bibliography³³. The global spread of Ibsen's dramas is documented in the database Ibsenstage³⁴, and translations of his works are available in The Multilingual Ibsen³⁵. A wealth of historical documents, exhibition materials, correspondence by family and friends, historical photographs, and everyday objects from their lives remain to be digitized, but may be available online as metadata. This valuable material is currently confined within separate siloes, defined by historical, material, and disciplinary boundaries (Evensen 2020) (See Figure 5).

Figure 2: Screenprint of Henrik Ibsen's writings

By opening up the data and establishing access beyond the current digital borders, significant achievements can be made. It would allow scholars to trace the reception and adaptation of works, shedding light on their cultural impact and evolution over time, and enable users to explore the performative aspects of the artist's works, enhancing their understanding of them as living entities. Reviews and exhibition history also play a pivotal role in shaping critical discourse and assessing an artist's impact, and give access to contemporary perspectives, facilitating a nuanced understanding of the reception and evolution of both Ibsen and Munch's literary/artistic reputation. Finally, the study of cultural networks and correspondences offers valuable insights into the personal and professional relationships of the artists.

³² <https://munch.mikromarc.no/mikromarc3/default.aspx?Unit=6473&db=munch>

³³ <https://www.nb.no/bibliografi/ibsen/search>

³⁴ <https://ibsenstage.hf.uio.no/>

³⁵ <https://www2.hf.uio.no/polyglotta/index.php?page=library&bid=10>

Objects

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Relevance

Figure 3: Screenprint of the presentation of Munch's artworks

Figure 4: Screenprint of the archive of Ibsen's artworks

CONNECTING WORKS, LIFE, AND ART

The vast resources available provide a unique opportunity to enhance the impact of the artists by integrating these various sources to their personal and professional lives. This task is challenging due to the diverse nature of the datasets and platforms involved, as the DSEs utilize text-based XML technologies, while media content is stored in different database solutions, and bibliographical metadata adheres to library standards. However, a future unification can be achieved through the combination of APIs, ontologies, and technologies of the semantic web. APIs³⁶ enable data access and integration between separate sources, allowing software systems to communicate and exchange data. Ontologies, in the form of structured vocabularies, establish a shared understanding of data by defining domain-specific concepts, relationships, and properties. The semantic web encompasses technologies such as RDF³⁷ and OWL³⁸, which enable data representation, linking, and processing in standardized formats, facilitating meaningful connections and relationships between datasets.

This approach would make it possible to incorporate the DSEs in broader platforms that offer unified access to all relevant datasets. Our future ambition is to establish interoperable research e-infrastructures that encompass significant datasets associated with each artist, covering their life and works, and facilitate open access and interoperability to all relevant

³⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/API>

³⁷ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

³⁸ <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

material. By establishing a shared vocabulary and formalizing relationships between entities, the platforms would ensure smooth data interoperability across multiple sources, enabling seamless exploration and analysis. The ontological framework would enable the cohesive integration of texts, manuscripts, performances, critical analyses, multimedia content, and other relevant resources. It would transcend disciplinary boundaries, connect previously isolated datasets, and foster new ways of interpreting and exploring the data across fields such as art history, theatre and adaptation studies, performance, literary and translation theory.

Figure 5: Screenprint of the Virtual Ibsen Centre, a website to access the separate Ibsen resources

As a first step to open up the Munch and Ibsen DSEs, we have included the metadata of both editions' correspondence corpora in the Norwegian Correspondences-project (NorKorr)³⁹ (Rockenberger et al 2019, Bøe 2022, Rockenberger 2023). NorKorr utilizes the CorrespSearch⁴⁰ infrastructure (See Figure 6) to integrate metadata in a common platform and establish connections not only among individual letters and similar materials, but also with correspondences throughout Norway, Europe, and beyond. Metadata in CorrespSearch are searchable through the web interface or via the open API, and available under a Creative Commons license in the Correspondence Metadata Interchange Format (CMIF)⁴¹ standard. By adding Norwegian letters into the existing corpus on CorrespSearch, they will be visible for the first time as part of a broader international correspondence network. This enables a macroscopic view of correspondence networks that have existed throughout the centuries.

³⁹ <https://github.com/norkorr/project>

⁴⁰ <https://correspsearch.net/en/home.html>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/TEI-Correspondence-SIG/CMIF>

Figure 6: Screenprint of Edvard Munch's letters in CorrespSearch

CONCLUSION

This paper argues that opening up DSEs by connecting them with a range of artist-related content is crucial for fostering comprehensive scholarship and promoting a deeper understanding of an artist's work within its broader context. By leveraging digital technologies, we can bridge the gaps between isolated resources and create rich and interconnected platforms that enhance the scholarly experience, facilitate interdisciplinary research, and ultimately contribute to a more nuanced understanding of literary works and their creators by connecting works, life, and art.

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Das Edendum als Modellierungsaufgabe. Am Beispiel des Niklas Luhmann-Nachlasses.

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EINFÜHRUNG

„Open up“ bedeutet, das eigene Editionsprojekt für möglichst vielfältige Nutzungsszenarien anschlussfähig zu machen. Das setzt voraus, sich über sein eigenes Editionsobjekt im Klaren zu sein, dieses konzeptuell konsistent beschrieben und modelliert und das Wissen dazu in Daten übersetzt zu haben. Der Editionsgegenstand, das abstrakt als Zielkonzept gefasste „Edendum“, definiert und bedingt den konzeptionellen Raum, das Projekt, die Edition. Auf dieses ist sie zugeschnitten, ihr Ziel ist es, das Zielobjekt bestmöglich zu erschließen und abzubilden.⁴²

Dieses *Abbild so generisch*, d. h. als formales Modell so „allgemeinverständlich“ und damit *anschlussfähig* wie möglich zu gestalten, ist die notwendige Voraussetzung dafür, die Edition über den Projektkontext hinaus zu öffnen und offen zu halten. Dazu müssen *Modelle und Sprachen (Ausdrucksweisen)* gefunden werden, deren Fähigkeit es ist, einerseits eine Übersetzung und Verbindung zwischen spezifischen Editionsobjekten zu leisten (Bensmann, Zapilko und Mayr 2017), um so andererseits projektübergreifende Anschlussfähigkeit zu ermöglichen (Bizer, Heath und Berners-Lee 2011). Die sich damit aufdrängende Frage, an welchen (bestehenden) Modellen und Ontologien man sich orientieren könnte, steht jedoch nicht selten in einem starken Kontrast zu den projektspezifischen Fragestellungen und Objektsichten (Tomasi 2018, Ciula et al. 2018).

Der *Anspruch der Digital Humanities* geht über eine fachspezifische, an bestimmten lokalen Forschungsfragen orientierte „aktuelle“ Erschließung, die in der Modellierung nur eine partikuläre Perspektive einnehmen, in der Datenerstellung nur einen zeitgenössischen Wissensstand abbilden und in der medialen Präsentation nur vorübergehende Nutzungsinteressen adressieren kann, hinaus und stellt die Frage nach *Daten*, die generischer, langlebiger und nachhaltiger sind (Eide und Ore 2019, Marcondes 2020). Diese Ziele konvergieren mit der Öffnung der Daten: Indem diese aus einer über den spezifischen Projektkontext hinausgehenden, „allgemeineren“ Sicht heraus modelliert und verlinkt werden und damit ihre Nachnutzung anregen (Heath und Bizer 2011), bleiben sie offen und bestehen (Cools und Padlina 2021).

Exemplarisch soll in diesem Beitrag anhand der Edition des Luhmann-Nachlasses (<https://niklas-luhmann-archiv.de/>) diskutiert werden, wie eine Vermittlung zwischen den Positionen zu einem sehr komplexen Editionsobjekt (hier: materialiter ein heterogener Nachlass, abstrakter ein Denkraum) aussehen kann und welche Perspektiven sich daraus für die Öffnung des Editionsprojektes ergeben.

DER NACHLASS ALS EDENDUM UND SEINE DIMENSIONEN

Edition beginnt mit der Modellierung von übergreifenden Erschließungs- und Beschreibungsverfahren, die einerseits die Konvergenz zur Umwelt (die kulturelle Überlieferung insgesamt) und andererseits die Kohärenz der unterschiedlichen Projektgegenstände sichern. Dazu muss das Edendum (hier: der Nachlass) zunächst *konzeptionell und begrifflich* in seinen potentiell *verknüpfbaren Dimensionen expliziert* werden. Im Luhmann-Nachlass sind das z. B. die Dimensionen der

- physischen Archivobjekte (Zettelkasten, Manuskripte, Audio- und Videoaufnahmen, Arbeitsbibliothek, Korrespondenz) und ihrer granulierenden Unterteilung (Zettelkasten → Zettel, Manuskripte → Seiten / Kapitel / Abschnitte, Bibliothek → Bände)
- Zuordnung von physischen Dingen zu bibliographischen Objekten
- Zuordnung zu (abstrakten) Werken
- Identifikation von benannten Entitäten in Werken oder Textobjekten
- Zuordnung von Sachthemen

⁴² Zum Begriff „Edendum“ vgl. Jaeschke 2001, 29, sowie Burkhard und Huck 2003, 107.

- Einbettung in die Biographie des Nachlassers
- Positionierung innerhalb des medientheoretischen und kulturhistorischen Kontextes

Diese konzeptionellen Räume resultieren unmittelbar aus den für das Projekt relevanten Sichten auf das Material. Sie bilden damit zwar ein projektspezifisches setting, speisen sich aber auch aus ontologischen Konzepten jenseits des Projekts (Ciula et al. 2018). Dabei gilt, dass diese Dimensionen ontologisch nicht (disjunkt) auf einer Stufe stehen und miteinander auf verschiedene Weise verbunden sind (s. Abb.1). Für jede dieser Dimensionen sind bereits bestehende externe Standards und Modelle zu berücksichtigen. Für die konkreten Editionsobjekte ist das *Spannungsverhältnis zwischen den spezifischen Anforderungen des vorliegenden Materials und den allgemeinen Standards* aufzulösen: Die zum Einsatz kommenden Modelle sollen so standardkonform wie möglich eingesetzt und so lokal spezifisch wie nötig angepasst werden.

Abb. 1: Allgemeinste konzeptuelle Zusammenhänge

Die *grundlegenden Zusammenhänge* zwischen den verschiedenen Erkenntnisobjekten in der Nachlasserschließung sind (wie man sieht) letztlich trivial. Das Zusammenspiel der Objekte ist aber nicht nur allgemein ontologisch zu fassen, sondern über *geeignete technische Formate und konzeptionelle Standards für die Repräsentation der einzelnen Objekte zu ermöglichen*. Die Frage lautet deshalb: Was sind die am besten geeigneten externen Modelle für die einzelnen Bereiche?

Auf der technischen Ebene werden Archivobjekte durch komplexe Digitalisate repräsentiert, die letztlich sowohl die visuelle (Form) als auch die intellektuelle (Inhalt) Dimension abdecken und damit realiter alle anderen Objekttypen einbinden: TIFF-Abbildungen (in JPG-Gebrauchsformen) liegen auf Bildservern und werden von dort in bibliothekarische (METS/MODS) oder editorische Formate (TEI) eingebunden, die sie als bibliografische Objekte identifizieren (TEI Header), ihren Inhalt recodieren und diesen mit weiterem Wissen in Form von Annotationen anreichern. Ggf. erfolgen Übersetzungen in zur technischen Weiterverarbeitung geeignete Formate (JSON) (s. Abb. 2).

Abb. 2: Ebene der verwendeten technischen Standards

DAS PROJEKTMODELL IM LICHT EXTERNER STANDARDS

Hinter dieser sehr praktischen Ebene stehen wiederum die *konzeptionellen Standards*:

- RNA(B) erklärt, wie Archivobjekte beschrieben werden können
- EAD bildet die erste Stufe einer archivischen Beschreibung ab (Findbuch)
- METS/MODS erlaubt die Beschreibung komplexer digitaler Objekte
- DC liefert ein Grundgerüst für die Metadaten von digitalen Objekten
- RDA bietet eine bibliothekarische Sicht auf die Objekte, eingebettet in den erweiterten GLAM-Kontext
- Mit den SPAR Ontologies (Coyle 2022) lassen sich spezifische textuelle Phänomene beschreiben (z. B. Referenzen, Zitationen oder Dokument-Bestandteile)
- FRBR klärt den konzeptionellen Zusammenhang zwischen den verschiedenen bibliographischen Objektebenen (Boot und Koolen 2018)
- LIDO, LRM (Coyle 2022), RiC (Llanes-Padrón und Pastor-Sánchez 2017) und CIDOC-CRM könnte uns helfen, die verschiedenen Objekte mehr aus einer ereigniszentrierten Sicht zu beschreiben
- Knowledge Organisation Systems wie TheSoz und LCSH machen die Sacherschließung anschlussfähig an den Fachdiskurs (hier: Soziologie)
- Normdatenrepositories wie GND oder Wikidata identifizieren Entitäten und verknüpfen den Luhmann-Nachlass mit dem allgemeinen Wissensgraphen (Spadini et al. 2021)

Auf diesen Grundlagen klärt zum einen ein projektinternes *bibliographisches Modell* die Zusammenhänge zwischen bibliographischen und physischen Objekten. Zum anderen stellt ein projektinternes *Werkmodell* den Zusammenhang zwischen Werken und bibliographischen Objekten her.

Abb. 3: Ideal-Zustand = Ebene der Modelle und Standards

Dieser Beitrag soll einen Überblick über die “Silo-Daten”-Problematik im Allgemeinen und die schwierige Lage des schon fortgeschrittenen Luhmann-Projektes bei der Herstellung nachhaltig nutzbarer Daten im Besonderen geben. Wir sprechen also über

- den Ist-Zustand: lokal angepasste TEI-Schemata in FRBR-Inspiration
- die wahrgenommenen Probleme: Mangel an Linkage und Mapping (Ciotti und Tomasi 2016)
- die mögliche Zukunft: die Berücksichtigung weiterer Modelle für die Verbesserung von Datenqualität und Nachnutzbarkeit

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Digitale Edition der Memoiren der Gräfin Schwerin: Anwendung und Nutzen von Named Entity Recognition

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EINLEITUNG

Im Rahmen eines vom FWF finanzierten Forschungsprojekts (Laufzeit: 2022-2025), welches am Institut für die Erforschung der Habsburgermonarchie an der ÖAW unter der Leitung von Ines Peper in Kooperation mit dem Institut Zentrum für Informationsmodellierung umgesetzt wird, wird eine digitale Edition der Memoiren der Gräfin Schwerin (1684-1732) entstehen.

Gräfin Luise Charlotte von Schwerin, geboren 1684, schrieb in den frühen 1720er Jahren ihre Lebenserinnerungen nieder, die einen besonderen Einblick in Handlungsspielräume von Frauen des Hofadels geben. Die Memoiren sind in zwei Abschriften in französischer Sprache überliefert, wobei die Abschrift “L’Histoire De la Vie de madame la comtesse de Scheverin écrite par elle même a ses enfans” (Manuskript A, Aix-en-Provence, Bibliothèque Méjanes) bereits 2013 in einer gedruckten Edition erschien (Daumas und Ulbrich). Manuskript W, welches sich im Wiener Haus-, Hof- und Staatsarchiv befindet, wurde erst 2016 entdeckt. Die digitale Edition soll die Transkription von Manuskript W, eine Lesefassung, die den Text und die Abweichungen beider Abschriften ausweist, und eine deutsche Übersetzung präsentieren.

DIGITALE EDITION UND NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION

Digitale Editionen von Memoiren, Tagebuch- oder auch Briefeditionen sind in der Regel dadurch gekennzeichnet, dass der ursprüngliche Sinnzusammenhang für Nutzer:innen nachvollziehbar gemacht wird, der in besonderen Schreibsituation bei den Leser:innen stillschweigend vorausgesetzt werden kann. So sind Kommentare, Register und einführende Texte wesentliche Bestandteile von Selbstzeugniseditionen. Dazu gehört auch die Annotation von *Named Entities* (z.B. Personen, Orte) im Editionstext und deren Anreicherung mit Normdaten (z.B. GND, GeoNames).

Die Erschließung bzw. Kodierung bedeutet aber in derartigen Projekten auch oft einen sehr großen Arbeitsaufwand. Immer wieder taucht die Frage auf, ob nicht das Verfahren des *Named Entity Recognition* (NER) dabei helfen könnte, diesen Arbeitsaufwand zu reduzieren. Bei *Named Entity Recognition* handelt es sich um eine computergestützte Methode zur automatisierten Erkennung von Eigennamen, welche in vielen Bibliotheken für NLP (*Natural language processing*) enthalten ist, wie z.B. in spaCy, flair, nltk oder WebLicht (Eder 2021). Die meisten NER-Modelle wurden bisher mit journalistischen Texten trainiert, die in einer ressourcenstarken Sprache (allen voran Englisch), vorlagen (Desmet und Hoste 2014). Vereinzelt wurde NER bereits im Hinblick auf digitale Editionen evaluiert oder verwendet (z.B. Nantke, Bläß und Flüh 2022, More 2021, Haeder 2020).

NER funktioniert bei der Anwendung auf historische Texte oft nur unzureichend, da sie sich sowohl in der Form, als auch im Inhalt von modernen Texten unterscheiden (Sánchez-Marco et al. 2011, Won, Murrieta-Flores und Martins 2018) – sie weisen z.B. häufig eine nicht standardisierte Orthographie auf oder verwenden *Nested Entities* (z.B. “Herzog Otten von Luneburg”, vgl. More 2021, 66).

Im Rahmen des Projekts kommt hinzu, dass die Entitäten in drei verschiedenen Fassungen des Editionstexts (Transkription von MS W, normalisierte Lesefassung und deutsche Übersetzung) miteinander in Beziehung gesetzt werden sollen. Das Paper wird Anwendung und Nutzen von NER in diesem Szenario evaluieren. Der Fokus des Papers soll auf die französischen Texte, also auf die Transkription und Lesefassung, gelegt werden. Nicht alle NER-Tools bieten französische Modelle an, so wurden für den vorliegenden Fall Modelle von spaCy, flair und CamemBERT verwendet.

Wie zu erwarten, ist die Anwendung der generischen Modelle auf die Editionstexte der Memoiren schon bei einer einfachen menschlichen Durchsicht nur mäßig zufriedenstellend: In der Transkription erscheinen Personen- und Ortsnamen meist nur abgekürzt, wodurch mittels der NER-Modelle oft nur Teile der Entitäten erkannt werden (z.B. nur “S.” von “C. d. S.”, wobei der String für “Comte de Schwerin” steht), oder die Entitäten falsch gelabelt werden.

Dasselbe gilt allerdings auch für die bereits normalisierte Fassung, in der Personen- und Ortsnamen aufgelöst wurden. spaCy liefert hier außerdem von den erkannten Entitäten ungefähr 50% False Positives, also Textstrings, die als Entitäten erkannt werden, aber keine sind. Flair klassifizierte 216 Entitäten, wovon ungefähr 40 False Positives darstellen. CamemBERT lieferte insgesamt die besten Ergebnisse - fast alle der erkannten und klassifizierten Entitäten sind *True Positives* und die Klassifikation nach Ort und Person funktionierte gut; allerdings wurden auch hier Textstrings aufgesplittet. Im Hinblick auf die Editionstexte der Memoiren der Gräfin Schwerin kommt erschwerend hinzu, dass Personen sehr oft nur mit nicht-rigidem Designator (Kripke 1982, z.B. "meine Schwägerin") erwähnt werden. Im Goldstandard für die Analyse wurden insgesamt 156 Personen getagged, wovon 70 nur indirekt genannt werden. Derartige Nennungen werden von den NER-Modellen, bis auf sehr wenige Ausreißer, nicht erkannt. Diese Ausführungen zeigen, dass ein rein automatisiertes Tagging der Texte mit generischen Modellen nicht fruchtbringend ist, da letztendlich sowieso eine recht umfangreiche Kontrolle und Verbesserung notwendig wäre. Die Möglichkeit, ein Modell zu trainieren, wird in den nächsten Monaten im Rahmen des Projekts mittels *Active Learning* erprobt werden – wir werden dafür Prodigy verwenden. Es wird dabei darum gehen, zu evaluieren, ob mit diesem Verfahren eine ausreichende *Ground Truth* erzeugt werden kann, um für den im Vergleich zu Standardaufgaben der NER eher kurzen Text noch effiziente Vorhersagen machen zu können, oder ob das Training ähnlich viel Zeit kostet wie die händische Annotation und spätere Überprüfung.

Mit den neuesten Entwicklungen von *Large Language Models* (LLMs) wie GPT-3 und GPT-4 von OpenAI eröffnen sich außerdem weitere Möglichkeiten – auch diese können für NLP Tasks genutzt werden. In einem ersten Experiment mit einem kurzen Textsample der normalisierten Lesefassung wurden von ChatGPT-4 auf Basis von Input- und Output-Beispielen im Prompt (Wang et al. 2023) sowohl indirekte (z.B. "ma chère tante" oder "son beau-père") als auch direkte Nennungen von Personen und Ortsnamen zuverlässig erkannt und proprietär ausgezeichnet (ChatGPT: NER Experiment). Weitere Experimente mit längeren Textsamples und unterschiedlichen Prompts sollen folgen.

Wie jedoch können NER-Verfahren aber schon in einem ersten Schritt fruchtbringend eingesetzt werden? NER-Modelle können grundsätzlich dazu dienen, einen ersten Einblick in die Texte und die darin erwähnten *Named Entities* zu erhalten, da zwar nicht alle Ergebnisse korrekt sind, aber dennoch relativ viele Entitäten erkannt und klassifiziert werden. Außerdem konnten NER-Verfahren schon jetzt den Workflow der digitalen Edition bereichern, indem aus den von spaCy erkannten Entitäten in der Lesefassung die richtigen Vorschläge identifiziert wurden, die als Basis für ein semi-automatisiertes Tagging genutzt wurden.

In einem letzten Schritt sollen die *Named Entities* aus den unterschiedlichen Texten idealerweise automatisiert miteinander in Beziehung gesetzt werden. Wir werden testen, ob das Matching über *Named Entity Recognition* in den Texten und einer Kombination aus positionalen und semantischer Information durchgeführt werden kann.

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From Critical Digital Edition to Critical Digital Library: Late Antiquity Rabbinic Homiletics

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INTRODUCTION

Tanhuma Yelammedenu Literature (TYL) is a rabbinic homiletic genre from late antiquity. The genre consists of a variety of inter-connected texts, documented in distinct print collections, in distinct manuscripts representing unique compositions, as well as fragments documented only in medieval anthologies or found in the Cairo Genizah (storage of used sacred books). The digital era provides us with the opportunity to cope with the complexity of the genre that the linear progression of the print form failed to meet. (Nikolsky and Atzmon, 2021; Bregman, 2023)

The presentation of the TYL set many challenges. In addition to the variety of materials: the homilies represents different types of affinities: they might be close witnesses of the same text, different written performances of common thread of a homily or independent homilies that share scattered common motifs and exegesis. The extent texts contains various combinations, frequently mixing homilies from other combinations. The texts also demonstrate high degree of modularity, as elements transferred from one homily to another, and reshaped to fit the new context. There are also different system for the inner division and numbering of the texts, according to different liturgical rites. In most cases, the division does not reflect the authentic division to homilies and the conventional literary structure. Accordingly, except for very odd, old and partial efforts we do not even have print critical editions of any of the texts.

METHOD AND APPLICATION

Following preparatory projects aimed at improving and applying HTR for reading the manuscripts (Wecker et al, 2022), text reuse detection for coping with intertextuality and style classification for automatic extraction of fragments from medieval anthologies (Tannor et al, 2022) we turn to design an efficient data model.

We designed a model supporting both the “traditional” linear progression reading of any given recension with its variations on one hand, and a bird-eye visualization of the entire corpus of diverse homilies and their intertextual relations per the each biblical reading lection.

In this lecture, we will present the guidelines of the data modeling designed for the project, which can serve as a prototype for a transition from a simple critical digital edition for a single text to a critical digital library of interconnected texts.

- 1) Strict separations of layers of knowledge: image, extracted content (layout, texts, margins, titles, etc), distinct layers of analysis (editorial comments; literary structure analysis).
- 2) Birds-eye arrangement and visualization of all extent homilies per the different hierarchies of the text. All extent materials for each biblical reading lection are presented as the basic unit of discourse and editing (Sacher and Lavee, in print).
- 3) Multi-hierarchical tagging, representing all types of divisions applied to the text (including both the traditional divisions and the authentic literary division exposed by literary analysis).
- 4) Combination of TEI representation of textual witnesses with external knowledge graphs:
 - a. Intertextuality knowledge graph (all-to-all tagged and defined relations).
 - b. Indexed scholarly comments attached to the various texts: introductory remarks, editorial comments, glossaries of terms, etc.
- 5) Representation of automatic vs curated (post-automation supervised and approved) knowledge.

Storing and representing the data according to these guidelines will be the bases for a dynamic digital library enabling the use to experience various modes of reading (from traditional edition of all witnesses of a given work to visualization and exploration of all extent materials of a given homily and their varied-type intertextual affinities; choosing between diplomatic representation of physical witnesses to curated and commented critical edition; surfing the texts according to

the inner division in witnesses, the canonical division in print edition and the analysis literary form based division provided by us. We will demonstrate the application of the guidelines on a given example.

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Spanish chapbooks and place names: enriching digital scholarly editions with geographical data

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INTRODUCTION

Untangling the cordel (2020-2024) is a research project, directed by Professor Constance Carta of the University of Geneva and supported by the Sandoz-Monique de Meuron Family Philanthropic Foundation. This project aims at studying and enhancing a collection of Spanish chapbooks (Figure 7), curated by the library of the University of Geneva (Leblanc and Carta 2021).

This collection consists of 915 chapbooks (or *pliegos de cordel*), dating from the 19th century and originating from many printers across Spain. To analyse these documents from literary and bibliographical perspectives, the project has chosen to create a digital library (DL) that provides enriched and searchable digital scholarly editions (DSE).

Figure 7: Examples of Spanish chapbooks

Developed with *TEI-Publisher* (e-editiones 2022), this DL displays diplomatic DSEs, transcribed with *eScriptorium* and encoded in XML TEI, as well as a catalogue of woodcuts⁴³. Online since April 2022, it allows users to search in the full text, compare facsimiles or engravings, and download them. The aim of this first phase of the project was to make available these printed documents –which are often invisible in traditional library catalogues– to a wide audience.

Now, the project is entering a new phase, where it is no longer simply a question of exposing data, but of demonstrating how these data can be reused to answer a specific research question: the use of place names in chapbooks. This work presents our experiments with the detection of place names and their integration into pre-existing DSEs, as well as the way we present them in the digital library.

CHAPBOOKS AND PLACE NAMES: WHAT CAN WE LEARN?

With the decision to use Named Entities Recognition (NER) technologies to exploit place names in our corpus, the project takes a step forward that will provide advanced services and open new research questions within the scientific team. Thanks to this approach, it will become feasible to study the distribution of places in the corpus by printers, text types (*romances*,

⁴³ For the moment, only the *Moreno* corpus part of the Geneva collection is online, which is unique in that it was produced by the same printer, José María Moreno, in the mid-19th century. The rest of the collection, known as the *Pliegos Varios* corpus, is currently being transcribed and encoded. It will be available online later this year.

oraciones, sainetes, etc.) or genre (secular or religious). We also want to analyse the distance and the relationship between the place of publication, indicated in the colophons of each chapbook, and the places mentioned in the body of the text. This new phase of the project promises to enrich our understanding of Spanish chapbook literature and its geographical context. The expected results will be presented as an interactive map that will allow a better understanding of the corpus not only as a whole, but also at the level of individual texts through indexes and specific analyses.

THE DETECTION OF PLACES USING FLAIR

To define the best configuration for detecting place names in our corpus, we conducted several experiments using the FLAIR framework (Akbik et al. 2019). First, we applied FLAIR's Spanish NER model (Schweter and Akbik 2020a) to a set of 50 texts, randomly selected from the two corpora of the project, obtaining an F1-Score of 92%.

In a second step, we corrected these results using *INCEpTION* (Klie et al. 2018) to create a Ground Truth (GT) that allowed us to improve FLAIR's base model. Fine-tuning this model did not improve over the default configuration (Figure 8). We therefore chose to fine-tune other models (*bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner* and *roberta-spanish-ner*), whose architecture seemed promising for our corpus and purposes.

Figure 8: Results in percentage of the different experiments conducted with the framework FLAIR. Repartition of the GT with 50 texts (in sentences) : 2506 (Train), 331 (Dev), 294 (Test) ; with 60 texts : 2958 (Train), 433 (Dev) and 641 (Test).

After several experiments, varying the number of texts and epochs (Figure 2), our best model obtained an F1-Score of 95.87%. We applied this model to the *Moreno* corpus to then produce a reliably annotated corpus: the results were exported in CoNLL 2002 format and manually corrected to eliminate errors, mainly in the titles as they will be the subject of specific analysis.

MAPS AND INDEXES: POST-PROCESSING OF THE DATA

These results will be integrated into the DL 1) at a **collection level**, with a dynamic map, created with the *Peripleo* application (Simon et al. 2022), and an index, created with *TEI-Publisher*, and 2) at a **document level**, with a list of the place names that appear in each document and their occurrences.

To develop these functionalities, firstly, we converted our CoNLL 2002 data into a CSV file containing the document's identifier and the place names as they appear in the text. This file was then completed using *Open Refine* to link each place to its *Wikidata* equivalent. We added the place identifier (for example, Q29 for Spain), geographical coordinates, type (country, town, etc.) and standardised name. This new CSV file has then been enriched with data from the pre-existing XML TEI files, i.e. the title of the document, its date, place of publication, printer, type, genre, and the URL of the document on the DL.

On the one hand, this information enables us to generate a JSON file in Linked Places Format (LPF) to create a map with *Peripleo*. On the other hand, some of this information is inserted into the TEI files to develop both a general index (Figure 9) and a specific list for each document: 1) in the body of the text with a <name> element, and 2) in the metadata within a <listPlace> element, specifying the *Wikidata* identifier and the geographical coordinates of each place.

```
<place xml:id="Jerusalén" n="Jerusalén">
  <placeName type="main">Jerusalén</placeName>
  <placeName type="alt">Jerusalen, Jeruzalen, Jérusalem</placeName>
  <location>
    <geo>31.77888888888889,35.22555555555556</geo>
  </location>
  <desc>
    <ref target="https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1218">Q1218</ref>
  </desc>
</place>
```

Figure 9: Description of Jerusalem in the TEI index that will be used by TEI-Publisher

CONCLUSIONS: PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The first results have enabled us to detect 2344 locations in the *Moreno* corpus, including 396 different locations. Further analysis will be conducted during the year. We can already notice that if most of the places are in Spain, the texts also refer to places in other countries of Europe, Asia, North Africa, and Latin America, that recount Spanish history.

A prototype map⁴⁴ has been built and will be gradually enriched with new data (Figure 10). *Peripleo* was chosen for its ease of use and its system of dynamic facets. The latter will enable us to analyse locations from different perspectives and answer our research questions. Regarding the publication of these results within the DSE and the DL, the functionalities are still in their early stages of development but will follow the model proposed by the *Alfred Escher-Briefedition*.

Figure 10: Visualisation of the place names mentioned in the Moreno corpus using *Peripleo*

The enrichment of our DSEs with new data demonstrates how our TEI files can be reused to answer specific research questions. The new version of our corpus is both 1) a **scientific result** of the project, as we are proposing an interpretation of the document through a geographical point of view, and 2) a **new tool** for exploring our data within the DL.

⁴⁴ The prototype is available at this address: <<https://desenrollandoelcodel.github.io/peripleo-pliedos>> [Accessed 06/07/2024]

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Meticulous Automatization – Machine Learning in the Digital Scholarly Edition *Grundtvig's Works*

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INTRODUCTION

The digital scholarly edition (DSE) *Grundtvig's Works* (2009-2029), rendered at www.grundtvigsvaerker.dk, deploys Machine Learning in a line of production task as well as in scholarly exploration of the annotated data (e.g., Baunvig & Nielbo 2022, Nielbo, Bo & Baunvig 2018). We have elsewhere pointed to the advantages in aligning Machine Learning in the production as well as in the computational analysis of the DSE material (Baunvig 2023, Rasmussen et al. 2022). This paper draws out the first of the two – that is, AI implementation in a series of production tasks. The automatization procedures were implemented half-way through the DSE project utilizing the Grundtvig data annotated by DSE personnel. This is a non-trivial fact: high-quality DSE automatization features are critically dependent upon Human-In-the-Loop (HITL) elements – that is: upon meticulous furnishing of metadata sensitive a range of contexts.

N.F.S. GRUNDTVIG AND THE GRUNDTVIG DATA

N.F.S. Grundtvig (1783-1872) was a poet, pastor, politician, and romanticist, who is regarded as one of the most (if not the) central figure in the nineteenth-century Danish nation building process, as well as in the construction of a modern Danish Christianity. *Grundtvig's Works* is the largest humanist research project in Denmark to date; it is funded directly by the Danish financial act. These facts testify to the cultural significance ascribed to Grundtvig.

Grundtvig was a man of many disciplines, whose writings spanned an impressive range of subjects. Consequently, the Grundtvig dataset is remarkably diverse, both in terms of genre and content. It encompasses dissertations, essays, and poems that delve into Scandinavian history, pre-Christian Nordic mythology, and Christian history; political manifestos, philosophical treatises, as well as linguistic studies focusing on Old Icelandic and Old English. Despite the breadth of his scholarship, his reputation among the general public rests primarily on his hymns and songs, with nearly 1,600 attributed to his authorship (Baunvig 2023).

The dataset *Grundtvig's Works* encapsulates the entirety of the works published during Grundtvig's lifetime (N = 1073), spanning the years from 1804 to 1872. This material, prepared via Optical Character Recognition (OCR), is currently undergoing XML markup by the staff of the Center for Grundtvig Studies at Aarhus University, in alignment with Text Encoding Initiative guidelines (TEI P5). At this stage, 54% of the material is fully annotated. However, the enrichment process remains ongoing, with the project scheduled for completion by December 31, 2029. The dataset comprises approximately 37K pages, exhibits a median document size of 4 pages, and contains 4M word-tokens distributed over 115K word-types.

The data is accessible at: <https://github.com/centre-for-humanities-computing/grundtvig-data>. Moreover, a custom XML parser for third-party data exploration can be found at: <https://github.com/centre-for-humanities-computing/GrundtvigParser>.

AUTOMATIZATION OF DSE TASKS

Grundtvig's Works deploys a line of automatization procedures in the production of the Grundtvig data: auto-tagging, commentary attachment, production of introduction, being the main ones.

Auto-tagging procedures are designed to identify and apply XML tags to personal names, geographic designations, and mythological content. This feature leverages the already-tagged corpus and the registries of personal names, place names, as well as mythological names and terms, and thereby integrating this tagging information directly into the non-text files. The auto-tagging procedure relies on the registry files `pers.xml`, `place.xml`, and `myth.xml`, in conjunction with the file `corpus.xml`. The latter encapsulates all the texts that have undergone comprehensive editing. Additionally, a stop

list is employed to delineate specific instances that should be excluded from the tagging process.

Automatic *commentary attachment* relies on the corpus of commentaries produced by the *Grundtvig's Works* staff (54 % annotated). The procedure is twofold: It involves 1) tagging of lemmas (words in need of commentary) in a given Grundtvig work and 2) the generation of a comment file proffering annotation suggestions.

Production of prose *introductions* to given works relies on the fact that Grundtvig is relatively consistent within genres. This means that a bulk of already-written introductions can play the role of baselines in the construction of genre sensitive templates.

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BeNASch - a Common Semantic Annotation Framework for Early Modern German

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INTRODUCTION

Researchers analysing historical data or training machine learning algorithms on pre-modern German texts for semantic information face multiple problems.

Firstly, the annotation system varies from project to project. Annotation projects, even if they are otherwise similar, may differ significantly in their rules for choosing and labelling spans. This problem is further deepened by the fact that none of the historical editions we investigated published their annotation guidelines openly.⁴⁵ Most often, the annotation procedure is only described vaguely. This contrasts with the handling of transcription rules, which are usually presented in great detail and oftentimes refer to shared standards.⁴⁶

Secondly, most of today's semantic annotation of German texts is limited to annotating named entities only, a practice that likely originates from the need to create registries for editions. While named entity annotations hold potential for some analysis of annotated texts, their usefulness is limited. A relevant entity in a text might be missed because it is not referred to as a named entity, while a non-relevant named entity might be included, although it only gets referred to in relation to a more relevant entity.⁴⁷ We have observed that some projects deviate from strict named entity annotation due to these issues. This carries the potential to introduce inconsistent and arbitrary annotations of non-named entities.

Thirdly, it is key to understand that produced data could (and should) be considered training material for machine learning processes. Automatic recognition and training approaches currently gain a lot of traction but require training material that needs to be structured according to desired outputs.

We believe it is in the best interest of the broader community of humanities scholars to structure data in a manner conducive to interoperable re-use (according to the FAIR principles) and in parallel allow its use as training material. This necessitates a particularly stringent commitment to maintaining consistent annotations.

Our proposed annotation system, called BeNASch (Berner (früh-)Neuhochdeutsches Annotationsschema), tackles the challenges mentioned above and proposes a first draft for discussion. Our framework is built to allow for the annotation of entities, relations, and events. By adding relations and events, more elaborate information can be extracted from annotated texts while keeping the use of the annotated data for historical analysis as well as machine learning in mind so that future data can be annotated manually as well as automatically. We also consider that different projects will require different specifications but can still profit from each other. Our system is inspired by the Automatic Content Extraction Program (ACE), specifically the annotation guidelines ACE 2005, which makes the data interoperable to other data sets (Doddington et al. 2004).⁴⁸

AIMS AND REQUIREMENTS

A unified annotation system excels when widely embraced in the research community. The more scholars use it, the more beneficial it is to other scholars. Therefore, our system not only caters to the requirements of Machine Learning (focusing on consistency, compatibility, and completeness) but was designed with a sustainable annotation process in mind. We want BeNASch to be as clear and intuitive as possible while ensuring it meets the requirements of (digital) history and, potentially, (socio-)linguistics.

⁴⁵ An example to this practice can be found in the Königsfelden-Edition (<https://www.koenigsfelden.uzh.ch/exist/apps/ssrq/intro.html>).

⁴⁶ For example, the DTA-Basisformat (<https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/doku/basisformat/>).

⁴⁷ Example: “Spital von Basel”, “Spital” is the more relevant entity here but would not be tagged.

⁴⁸ For the annotation guidelines themselves see: <https://www ldc.upenn.edu/collaborations/past-projects/ace/annotation-tasks-and-specifications>.

EXAMPLE

We present an example as it could appear in the "Historical Land Registers of the City of Basel"⁴⁹ to demonstrate the entity and relation annotation:

"Da hat Johann Furrer, der Schaffner des Spitals von wegen versessener Zinsen [...]"

This text span features the following entity mentions:⁵⁰

Annotation	Full Span	Head
REF.NAM.PER	Johann [...] Spitals	Johann Furrer
ATT.NOM.PER.ORG-REPR	der Schaffner des Spitals	Schaffner
REF.NOM.ORG	des Spitals	Spitals

The relation annotation captures the additional relational information:

Schaffner	is representing the organization	Spital
-----------	----------------------------------	--------

FRAMEWORK

We do not only propose this guideline but also plan to offer tools and tutorials to facilitate the use of the annotation system. Because BeNASch features nested entity annotations and requires the annotation of "heads", an annotation takes longer than flat (named) entity annotation. We alleviate this additional work by using "shortcuts" during annotation. One such shortcut is to declare certain default values. The example above omits the numeric annotation, as most mentions are singular entity mentions. If there is a group/plural mention, thus deviating from the default, this can additionally be annotated. We use a post-processing script that adds all omitted tags according to their defaults when converting the exported data into a standoff XML format.

DIFFERENT NEEDS

It is impossible to create an annotation system that can serve every project, especially for tasks of classification. Our goal here is to provide concepts that can be used no matter what classes are defined, and guidelines on how to expand classes instead of creating new ones, so compatibility with other projects largely remains. We suggest that projects featuring similar domains should use the same classification system, so they remain completely compatible.

We also plan to offer guidelines for research teams that feel a full annotation according to BeNASch-Standard is out of their scope and would prefer to annotate named entities only. The goal there is to ensure compatibility of these "BeNASch-light" corpora with the full annotation.

DESIGN PROCESS

The design of the framework officially started in April 2023 at the Digital Humanities (Walter Benjamin Kolleg) at the University of Bern. The fundamental concept was designed by researchers working with data from different domains, including historians, a computational linguist, and a historical sociolinguist. The goal of this project in the long run is to also involve researchers from outside the University of Bern who may be interested in adopting such a system of annotation. Github is used as a platform of discussion, and everyone is invited to read the work-in-progress guideline document and leave comments.⁵¹

⁴⁹ <https://www.staatsarchiv.bs.ch/benutzung/recherche/suche-gedruckte-kataloge/historisches-grundbuch.html>

⁵⁰ REF = reference to an entity, ATT = attributive mention of the head of the overarching span, NAM = named mention, NOM = nominative mention, PER = mention of a person, ORG = mention of an organization, ORG-REPR = mention of an entity representing an organization.

The head marks the string that is indicative for the annotation.

⁵¹ <https://github.com/raykyn/BeNASch>

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eDITem: a generic approach to digital editions

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INTRODUCTION

This intervention aims to present the objectives and the conceptual architecture of eDITem (Digital Infrastructure for Edition Templates), an ongoing project designed by researchers of the *Innovating Digital Edition* group of the Huygens Institute, in collaboration with the *Digital Infrastructure Department* (both divisions of the Humanities Cluster, Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, Amsterdam).

The main goal of the project, currently in its first stages of development, is to build a generally usable infrastructure for publishing XML/TEI based digital editions with a reduced effort for developers and a robust support for editors, through a ‘templates-based’ approach. The core of eDITem is in fact the implementation of templates suitable for groups of similar materials and edition typologies that can be combined as building blocks to create a modifiable and controlled digital edition of diverse sources.

It is indeed a fact that nowadays scholarly digital editions tend to be modelled and developed through specific and various workflows and with a high degree of customization both on the modeling and data creation side and for the development of the user interface, functionality and usability.⁵² This is clearly more evident with regard to interfaces, and, although the issue has been raised for some time, for example by Rosselli Del Turco (2016),⁵³ it is not yet solved. This variety of interfaces is often the end result of deep differences in the modeling of the edition itself, starting with the general design of the data and going through the encoding process and the development of functionalities.

This practice of ‘hyper-customized editing’⁵⁴ not only has high costs in terms of energy and funding, but also leads to negative consequences regarding maintenance, preservation and reusability.⁵⁵ However, similar sources and materials could be described via similar editorial approaches and have comparable needs in terms of final output.

eDITem: GOALS AND GENERAL ARCHITECTURE

The goal of eDITem is precisely to face this scenario and try to provide a solution to overcome maintenance and reusability issues on the one hand and to accelerate and better control the editorial process in the other. In fact, the template approach, as mentioned, could also have the benefit of ensuring a greater autonomy to the editor, who does not always have a sufficient expertise in the technologies required to prepare a digital edition and is heavily dependent on developers.

Within this framework, eDITem will try to address both theoretical and practical problems and this, together with its potentially very broad applicability, makes the project particularly interesting for discussion and debate, considering that the theoretical challenges raised by eDITem lie in its very foundations: the definition of template, how it should be built and how the templates should interact with each other, to name the most interesting.

Another crucial and not easy goal of our project is to build general and reusable templates, but also to guarantee sufficient space for more specific components that an edition might require. This is why we are defining the eDITem architecture including three different layers, corresponding to three levels of genericity. The most general level should define data structures that are used in most or all templates with their most common behaviours, the second level should address

⁵² This, besides the experience common to both scholars and users of digital editions, immediately emerges from browsing the two most important catalogues of digital critical editions, the one provided by Greta Franzini (<https://dig-ed-cat.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/>) and the one edited by Patrick Sahle (<https://v3.digitale-edition.de/>). Even navigating through the editions provided by major DH institutions, the feeling is that of dealing with quite different presentations of, in many cases, similar materials.

⁵³ The mentioned article addresses the problematic consequences of “the high fragmentation of user interfaces and the resulting difficulty in the use of each SDE [...]” already highlighting that “while there is a slow trend towards a sort of ‘canon’ or standard set of tools expected to be available [...], no standardised user interface exists” (Rosselli Del Turco 2016, 230). See also Del Turco, Di Pietro (2018) and, with regard to EVT, Rosselli Del Turco, Di Pietro (2019) and Rosselli Del Turco, Di Pietro, Martignano (2019).

⁵⁴ Or “haute couture” editions (Pierazzo 2019).

⁵⁵ See at least Oltmanns *et al.* (2019). For a broader perspective on sustainability see Drucker (2021).

combinations of data and behaviour definitions that should be reusable for multiple (collections of) documents and a third level should be provided for the needs of a specific corpus and should consist in an adaptation, namely an override of some definitions and behaviours of a template.

Given this background, our talk will present how the conceptual framework of the project has been developed to date, starting with our idea of template: a reusable component defined at the intersection of document type and required functionality, containing support for data creation as well as for publication. This means that each template should offer precise instructions on how to model and prepare the different types of materials we want to edit (letters, poems, dramas, etc.), providing control over data creation. In other words, it should make it clear to the editor how to encode the data. Moreover, a template should be able to specify behaviours, functionality, and rendering requirements, describing how each element should behave (itself and in relation to other elements) and should be styled in the final edition.

Regarding data creation, at this stage, an eDITem template consists of an XML/TEI schema, to ensure the validity and usability of the documents to be published, and additional constraints, written in Schematron (<https://www.schematron.com/>) to comply with XML schemas, to further check the encoding. The template also includes documentation, in the form of encoding guidelines with examples and explanations, and sample files, as simplified XML/TEI documents.

As far as publication is concerned, our research group will work in close collaboration with the DI department of the Humanities Cluster to figure out if and in which terms our approach can serve as a basis for the software development as well. In more specific words we are currently trying to define not only the data definition but also the processing model in TEI ODD files (*One Document Does it All*),⁵⁶ taking into account the desired functionalities and rendering. However, experiments conducted so far with the DI group have shown that this may not be the best way to proceed, and we will therefore study together possible alternatives.

To make our presentation more concrete, we will present the first templates developed within *The Mondrian Papers* (<https://mondrianpapers.org/>), an under development scholarly digital edition of Piet Mondrian's entire correspondence and theoretical writings, which constituted the context and the first test for our approach. The digital edition of Mondrian's materials has been chosen as a suitable environment in which to develop eDITem, since it includes multiple types of sources, which necessitates multiple templates. During the process we implemented some draft templates for letters and for printed essays, along with other templates for the supporting components that are widely included in digital editions, regardless of the type of sources published. These components include a template for people mentioned in the sources, a bibliography and a template for mentioned artworks as an example of a specialized template that could also be a framework for references of a similar type in other sources.

The hands-on approach of combining eDITem with the Mondrian edition also represented an important opportunity to define and experiment with the more difficult and critical aspects of our project, which involve both data creation and front-end development and will be indeed part of our presentation. In fact, in conclusion, as a request for input and suggestions, we will discuss the open issues of the project and the difficulties encountered so far, hoping to contribute to the debate on the sustainability and usability of scholarly digital editions.

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⁵⁶ This also facilitates the possibility of using TEI Publisher (<https://teipublisher.com/index.html>), a tool for publishing TEI-based digital editions, as a pre-publication tool for visualize encoded documents, to increase and simplify the editor's control during the editorial process. TEI Publisher also represents a model for our project to look to, given its proximity to eDITem in intentions and goals.

Oltmanns, Elias, Hasler Tim, Peters-Kottig Wolfgang and Kuper Heinz-Günter. 2019. "Different Preservation Levels: The Case of Scholarly Digital Editions". *Data Science Journal*, 18 51: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-051>

Lost in Translation: ekdosis, TEI xml, on Different and Irreducible Textual Paradigms. An Impossible Unique Standard.

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Abundance of data is far from being the hallmark of the digital age. To take here only the example of the *Textus receptus* of the New Testament, as early as the XVIIIth century, scholars such as Johann Albrecht Bengel (1687-1752), had to deal with a very large number of versions and scholia as well as countless variant readings. In many aspects, they were facing unprecedented problems posed by the existence of early citations and ancient translations in various languages, some of which even showed that certain passages of the received Greek text had been deliberately falsified. In this sense, modern critical editing reveals from the onset its multiple nature, in opposition to received printed text, and emerges out of the rejection of the idea that any improvement of classical texts should be conducted on the basis of vulgate texts transmitted in printed books.

This fundamental break must however be put into perspective. This paper argues that while critical editing surely breaks with the notion of received text, the advent of the digital age and digital critical editions remain the result of an ongoing process, not of a sudden break in tradition.⁵⁷

Many features are found alike in printed and digital editions. Both come equipped with several layers of critical notes—the *apparatus criticus*— in which is mentioned all the evidence that was used to build the edited text. However, this also is where the two kinds of editions part ways. Far from being seen as pure collections of data, well-formed critical apparatus of the printed tradition must be read as a paragraph of its own, freely composed in Latin at least when it comes to editing a classical text.

Arguably, getting oneself familiarized with its many conventional rules is not unrelated to learning a language equipped with terms, grammar rules and style embellishments. It came into existence out of over three centuries of tradition and cultural facts and is immediately accessible to human mind’s natural ability to use language and interpret conventional symbols, while it is quite inaccessible to a computer, unless every item of information has been encoded in the rather dumb format that is suited to machines.

On the other hand, it is commonly said that the contents of editions in print is the result of the binding of the book itself as an object, whereas digital editions, in which format and presentation are by definition separated from content, are free from limitations coming from such bindings. This leads to the notion of database-driven texts, and what D.J. Mastronarde and R.J. Tarrant have called “actionable texts for use in digital research”.⁵⁸

But once settled this difference between print and digital editions, it may not be possible to bring into agreement epistemological paradigms or set up universal models likely to prevail in critical editions as such.

The same goes for “metamodels” such as TEI xml, which may allow for the definition of specific schemes to be applied to various editing scenarios, but cannot be taken as unified solutions. In other words, relying on xml can be seen as a way to embrace a specific idea on the nature of the edition text and how it should be interpreted.

Generally speaking, any technical choice, whether it relates to formats, editing environments or text editors, contribute to defining a new epistemological paradigm that supplies the edition with structure and gives the text its meaning. In turn, any epistemological paradigm is necessarily local and cannot be transposed to another one without loss of information in the process. In this respect, the ideal of interoperability may be out of reach because translating a format to another entails choices and adaptations with the consequence of losing something unique, as in any translation.

In this paper, we will propose a reflection on a specific approach to digital scientific editing, through the `LATEX` package *ekdosis* (Alessi 2021).⁵⁹ We will describe the hermeneutical approach entailed by this way of compiling texts which results in generating from a single source fundamentally different outputs meant to serve different purposes. This applies not only to the typeblock on the physical page, made of a combination of an edition text and accompanying critical

⁵⁷See Vitali-Rosati (2018: 10, 33–6, 42, 51, 58, 70).

⁵⁸Mastronarde and Tarrant (2017).

⁵⁹See also Alessi (2020).

notes that reveals both the text and the uncertainties of its transmission without which no serious use can be made of ancient texts, but also to the way deviant reading are either presented to the reader or encoded for machines. As an example: Lat. deest, compared to omisit conveys less suggestion that an omission is faulty. However, xml encoding requires to decide whether or not this distinction should be part of the data scheme: is this item data or not? As important as it may be, this difference may be in practical reading and writing all too subjective to be transposed into data.⁶⁰

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⁶⁰See Vitali-Rosati (2023).

Poster Session

“Kabbalah of Holy Names” - Digital edition, database, and mind map

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Moses Zacuto was born in Amsterdam around 1610. In his youth, he moved with his family to Hamburg and at some stage went to Poland. It is not known precisely when he returned to Hamburg nor how long he stayed there until 1645, when he settled in Venice. He quickly became part of the Jewish public life and served as a leader of the local community for close to three decades. In 1673, he was appointed as the Rabbi of Mantua, where he stayed until his death in 1697.

Zacuto was the most prominent figure among Italian Jews in the second half of the seventeenth century and his many letters are evidence of his extensive contacts outside it as well.

A study of Zacuto’s writings on practical Kabbalah may find it helpful to understand the term “practical Kabbalah” as denoting Jewish magical knowledge that conveys kabbalistic thought, language, symbolism, or visual expression. Zacuto’s Alfa Beta Shel ha-Shemot (“The Alphabet of the [Holy] Names”) and his Sefer ha-Sodot (“Book of Secrets”) are impressive test cases of the symbiotic relationship between theoretical and practical approaches in the thought of this prominent and influential kabbalist. What is more, Zacuto’s writings demonstrate the validity of a generic distinction between material and linguistic magic and give expression to both these genres.

The Kabbalah of holy names—a bridge, as it were, across theoretical and practical Kabbalah in Zacuto’s thought, to which he contributed his book “The Alphabet of the Names.” This book, which is a lexicon of holy names, expanded over time into the work known today as “Book of the Roots of the [Holy] Names.”

Zacuto's books are organized as a dictionary in alphabetical order, which is distinguished by a structuralist structure that invites unique research methods. As part of the project, we are preparing a digital edition of the dictionary, which contain two sides:

[A] A digital edition with ‘Deep tagging’.

[B] A database that allows not only a high-level search within the entries that make up the edition, but also traces the author's 'mind map', through 'distant reading' methods. In this way the edition is a research tool, with the readings being done by the search tool.

Figure 1: screenshot from the tagging system.

For the tagging, we used the 'INCEption' system [<https://inception-project.github.io>]. The tagging does not include only names [NER - As with most of the digital editions], but a representation of the unique world of the author. These unique elements are related to the structured nature of the dictionary, and they are the ones which invite the unique research method. Examples of unique labels are the origin of the 'Holy Name' in the Bible, terms from the field of Kabbalah, and magical use of the Holy Name.

אות ו

ZacutSH-141

שם ויעמד פינחס וי יה עו מה ד, פי יה נו חה ס, וי יה פו לה ל, וי תה עו צה ר, הי מה גו פה ה בכל תיבה כלול הויה וסודו למגפה כתוב בקלף כשר באשורית ולמטה כי מלאכיו עיין עוד באות א'.

ZacutSH-142

שם והשיג וְלֹד אָבוּ יֶאֱזַן וְלֹל וְלֵב שְׂדֵי שְׂדֵי וְשֵׁד וְדֵשׁ דְּנֵשׁ דְּשֵׁי מוּצָאוּ מֵר"ת והשיג לכם דיש את בציר ושישה צירופי הם צירופי מלת דיששדי כחם להציל ממגפה ונכתבים בק"כ וניתני' בפתח

ZacutSH-143

שם וזכרתי וְנֵת יָאִי קְמַא תְּכַר יִיְה אֶתְמַס תְּנֵא בְּנֵק רְצַד יְהֵר תְּקוּ יִנְה יֶאֱא עֶפֶר קֶאֱזַן נְמֵא כְּבוּ וְנֵךְ אִירֶכְבֵּב שֵׁם זֶה נִקְרָא זֹכֵר בְּרִית אֲבוֹת וּיּוֹצֵא מִפְּסוּר' וּזְכַרְתִּי אֶת בְּרִיתִי יַעֲקֹב וְגו'

Figure 2: Screenshot from the beta version of the digital edition.

The realization of the digital edition was done with the help of TEI-Publisher, which will soon be available online (including the tagging). The next stage will be adding the query system, which will allow not only close reading, but also 'distant reading' within the text. The uniqueness of this 'distant reading' is that it will be dynamic, that is, it is the result of a query by the user and not a tool in the hands of the researcher only. To the project site: <https://kabbalaheditions.org/>

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Digital Editions of Networked Texts and Images in Early Modern Jewish Mystical Cosmographs

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INTRODUCTION

Jewish mysticism is characterized by its “objective” approach to the Divine. Rather than prioritize subjective experience, Jews presented their mystical insights in cartographic detail. In this spirit, they drafted divinity maps on large parchment sheets. Central to kabbalistic practice since the fourteenth century, these maps—known as ilanot (trees)—only recently attracted scholarly attention.

Their complex integration of texts and images makes the research and publication of ilanot daunting tasks. The cooperating teams successfully developed a basic infrastructure to address these unique challenges in a previous collaboration. Our new project - which is also at the center of this proposal - aims to develop the functionalities required for a new corpus: early modern ilanot. In addition to visualizing a far more complicated topography, early modern ilanot are maps-in-motion that bring a timeline sensibility to the representation of the emanatory chain of heavenly worlds.

The Grand Venetian Parchment of R. Elijah Menaḥem Ḥalfan and R. Abraham Ṣarfati

METHOD AND APPLICATION

Our proposal for a poster includes a presentation of both the previous phase of the project which focused on medieval kabbalistic diagrams and the current phase of the project that focuses on the early modern period.⁶¹

As part of the expansion of the project, we are working on the development and implementation of several features. Some of them are required to represent ilanot from the early modern period, while some of the features are required to represent the ilanot which are already on the portal:

- (1) the application of text-reuse and NLP technologies to identify textual elements with shared characteristics, in the ilanot (Based on the ACT system developed in the laboratory)⁶²;
- (2) the development of an ontology-based navigation and visualization interface; The interface will be based on the ontology already developed throughout the project.⁶³
- (3) the improvement of the full-text search via NLP results and the development of a specialized Elasticsearch Analyzer. This is required, because this is a unique language layer of Rabbinic Hebrew;
- (4) the description of ilanot in terms of topological map-like spatial features;

⁶¹ The editions that have already been created can be seen here: <https://ilanot.org/>

⁶² <https://textreuse.info/en/>

⁶³ <https://dev.ilanot.org/voc/ontology/index-en.html#intro>

(5) the description of ilanot features iconographic and textual variation;

(6) Development of a companion database, based on the database currently found in the Haifa University Library. The database will be integrated with the ontology and will allow both familiarity with the objects that do not have an edition, and a broad view of the editions themselves.⁶⁴

The technological innovation of the Maps of God project is its approach to the gathering, networking, and searchable rendering of the thoroughly integrated texts and images of ilanot. Our work began with the formulation of an ontology that modeled the world of ilanot and the relationships between its parts. In tandem, tools were designed to mark-up everything that can be seen on an ilan.

The digital edition in this context is not something that stands on its own. The edition is a reflection of the unique ontology, while allowing for a visual representation of the knowledge which is itself visual. The presentation will include an explanation of the various stages of the project in addition to explanations about how to create a digital edition of this kind; the complexity of representing complex visual materials, and the digital solutions provided for this in our editions. We will also demonstrate some of the new features that have been added to the system in the current stages.

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⁶⁴ For the ilanot database at the Haifa University Library: https://haifa-primo.hosted.exlibrisgroup.com/primo-explore/collectionDiscovery?vid=HAU&inst=972HAI_MAIN&collectionId=81175368600002791&lang=iw_IL

From a pile of papers to a database – on modelling an author's literary archive

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INTRODUCTION

In the last few centuries, the literary archive has been regarded as an integral part of an author's complete work (Benne 2021, 38) and not just as rarities or curiosities of the originator. The origin of the individual author's archive can vary. Perhaps the author themselves used it as a working archive during their lifetime, as seen, for example, with the Danish philosopher Søren Kierkegaard, or it is posthumously collected by an admirer who sees a particular quality in the authorship. Today, the archives are often located in collections at public institutions that aim to preserve our cultural heritage.

With this poster, I will present my PhD project, which will commence in the fall of 2023. In the project, I will examine the manuscripts in the Grundtvig Archive, which houses the written remnants of N.F.S. Grundtvig (1783-1872), who had and still has an extraordinary influence on various aspects of Danish society. One aim of my PhD project is a complete digitization of the Grundtvig Archive, and I will examine the advantages and disadvantages that the use of AI creates. To state the obvious: The use of AI has the possibility to make the process cheaper and faster. A disadvantage is that the transcription is not a critical establishment of the text. Furthermore, I will argue that the understanding of each manuscript relies partly on the interpretive key, the bibliographic and descriptive metadata.

CATEGORIZATION AND DIGITIZATION OF THE ARCHIVE

The content of the archive needs to be read, organized, and categorized to be utilized and related to the author and their body of work. Otherwise, it is just a pile of papers. If the pile is small, the problem may not be significant, as the contents can be easily comprehended. However, the comprehensibility of the contents of the pile decreases as the size of the pile increases.

It can be argued that there is an inherent rigidity in categorization systems (Folsom 2007, 1571). By that, I mean that the act of systematization itself is an expression of the interpretation of the archive's content. Categorization controls access to the archive. The bibliographic metadata serves as the key to interpretation. The question of metadata becomes even more relevant when we face the ubiquitous digitization of our cultural heritage, including the digitization of literary archives.

The Grundtvig Archive is the largest private archive left by any Danish author and is located at the Royal Library in Copenhagen (Petersen 1943, p. 40). The archive contains 565 fascicles, estimated to hold 90,000 pages. It is a large pile. The archive has been categorized at least twice. Most recently, in the mid-20th century, where each manuscript was categorized and described in the *Catalogue of N.F.S. Grundtvig's Papers* (1957-1964), following a preprinted form with 12+6 headings that express the bibliographic and descriptive metadata deemed relevant by the registrars of the time (Høirup 1957, 21).

The content of the archive has only to some extent been incorporated into research. The sheer number of manuscripts makes it an intellectual challenge to comprehend. Additionally, Grundtvig's Gothic handwriting is difficult to read. The archive calls for a legible and critical digitization that includes a searchable transcription of the text (Dahlström 2009). This kind of digitization used to be a manual and time-consuming task, but the technological advancements in Hand-written Text Recognition (HTR) and machine learning have facilitated the process. With the use of AI, I believe it is possible to enhance the critical digitization and exploration of the archive.

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Johann Caspar Lavater

Historical-critical Edition of Selected Correspondences (JCLB)

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The JCLB research project is a born digital edition. The project imports and publishes digital images and metadata of all letters from and to Johann Caspar Lavater (more than 23.000 letters), mostly via importation from the Zurich Central Library (ZBZ), implemented by the Trier Center for Digital Humanities (TCDH). The metadata are visualized on an interactive map of Europe, showing Lavater's vast network of correspondences. A selection of Lavater's correspondences is manually transcribed and critically edited (indices, commentary). The manual transcriptions and critical annotations are generated with the tool *Transcribo*, developed and customized for JCLB by the TCDH.

To ensure that all of Lavater's letters – including those that are not included in the historical-critical edition – are readable and searchable in the JCLB platform, an interface between *Transcribo* and the HTR tool *Transkribus* is established.

First, *Transkribus* is trained on Lavater's handwriting and applied to the corresponding letters using a model that is as specific as possible with a low error rate. After a critical evaluation of the results, *Transkribus* models will be trained for use on about a dozen different handwritings of Lavater's scribes, either individually or in combination (i.e. one model for all scribes). The advantages and disadvantages of models specific to individual handwritings and periods versus combined models will be evaluated.

Experiments with *Transkribus* are currently underway (application of the trained models to new data); results will be available by January 2024 and can be reported on in Open Up Digital Editions.

Depending on the quality of the *Transkribus* output, there are basically two possible strategies for integrating it into the online edition:

- (1) Integration of the HTR transcriptions in the search module as part of the full-text search.
- (2) Further integration and synoptic presentation (facsimile/transcription) of the HTR transcriptions analogous to the manually transcribed and edited letters, but with clearly recognisable labelling to distinguish them from the historical-critical edition.

Ad (1): When displaying search results, it is important that automatic transcriptions (by *Transkribus*) are clearly distinguished from the edited texts created and annotated manually with *Transcribo*, and that corresponding filter options are offered.

Ad (2): The starting page of the online edition JCLB shows the division between the areas 'Edition' and 'Network'. This is maintained throughout the site. The letters in the 'Network' area would benefit from an automatically generated transcription in addition to digital images and metadata.

It must always be possible to distinguish between the two areas so that users know at all times whether they are reading a relatively unedited machine transcription or a manually transcribed letter with critical commentary, explanations of passages, indices etc.

Lessons Learnt from Bullinger Digital

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INTRODUCTION

The inception of the *Bullinger Digital*^{65,66} project lay at a crossroads which demanded the merging of three distinctive resources: Firstly, previously **edited letters** from Heinrich Bullinger's correspondence (Gäbler et al., 1974-2020), already accessible via PDFs in an online search system.⁶⁷ Secondly, a physical **card index** created and conserved by the Swiss Institute of Reformation Studies provided metadata about the nearly 12,000 preserved letters. Thirdly, the **original letters** held by the Zurich State Archive and the Zurich Central Library. The project started with a pilot phase, digitising the index cards and correcting the digital entries through a crowd-sourcing campaign. With the metadata gleaned from these cards, we established a database serving as a starting point for the subsequent stages. The challenges encountered in this process provided valuable insights, which we want to share in this discussion.

DATA FORMATS

A long-standing project (in our instance, 48 years) involving a multitude of contributors inevitably generates various data formats over time. We had to wrestle with *TUSTEP*,⁶⁸ TXT, HTML and PDF files for textual resources. The transition from these diverse formats to custom XML files necessitated mindful handling of special characters (e.g., characters like “û” (*o* over *u*) got lost in the editions' OCR results, so we had to re-introduce them), different text sections and print layouts (headers, summaries, letter content), various footnotes (text-critical vs factual comments), and more. Customised control scripts ensured that no information was lost, e.g., verifying that footnotes were in sequential order and complete. The variety and evolution of formats made the extraction and structuring of pertinent information a challenging task.

MERGING DIFFERENT FORMATS

Our strategy was to develop a custom XML format encapsulating all extracted information in a GitHub repository for change management and version tracking, which proved very valuable. To boost our corpus interoperability, we transitioned from our custom XML to TEI XML after the data collection phase was complete while keeping our custom XML for internal search, corrections and annotations.

The scan images of all letters (>30,000 pages) in the tiff format amount to big data (roughly 939GB). To store and access the images via a IIIF server proved to be a convenient way to display them with various resolutions in our search system.

MAINTAINABILITY

We advocate for an early decision regarding the corpus sustainability beyond the project. Knowing in advance that we would leverage the TEI Publisher⁶⁹ to ensure continuous data availability would have steered us towards TEI XML from the outset. We must emphasise that our TEI format, derived from our custom XML, did not conform to TEI standards expected by the TEI Publisher, thus reinforcing the need for an early commitment to an appropriate final format.

POWERFUL XML TOOLS

When dealing with XML documents it is crucial for productivity to work with powerful XML tools including an editor. We chose Oxygen with a DTD (Document Type Definition) and style sheets to ensure well-formed XML documents throughout the editing processes.

⁶⁵ <https://www.bullinger-digital.ch>

⁶⁶ See also Fischer et al. (2022) Scheurer et al. (2023), Ströbel et al. (2023), Volk et al. (2022).

⁶⁷ <http://teoirgsed.uzh.ch>

⁶⁸ <https://www.tustep.uni-tuebingen.de>

⁶⁹ <https://teipublisher.com>

DEPENDENCE ON THIRD PARTY SOFTWARE

Our workflow for training handwritten text recognition models incorporated the Text2Image alignment model in *Transkribus* (Mühlberger et al., 2019). However, the discontinuation of this tool in 2023 left us without a substitute, underscoring the risk of reliance on third-party applications (especially when they are not open-source).

TOOLING

We devised a scan verification app to streamline the process from scan receipt to website publication. This tool facilitated image rotation if overlooked during digitisation, metadata verification against the letter, and tracking the data collection process. We thus endorse the use of (custom) software to enhance efficiency where possible. Furthermore, we employed a CMS (Content Management System) to maintain metadata and envisage its future use for data enrichment.

ChatGPT

Towards the end of our project ChatGPT entered the stage. We learned that many tasks in creating and presenting digital editions can be supported with such modern AI systems. In particular we discovered that ChatGPT is good at translating from Latin and Early New High German to modern German, at person and place name recognition and linking to Wikipedia and at letter classification (according to given categories).

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Using Digital Tools for Manuscript Research and Scholarly Edition Preparation in Hebrew

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INTRODUCTION

A prerequisite for any engagement with the text is a critical examination of its textual evidence, and an intelligent use of these textual evidence. The highlight of this field is the preparation of critical editions for texts. In the field of Jewish sciences, considerable efforts have been devoted to installing scientific editions of Tanim midrash, Amorim midrash and chapters from the Babylonian Talmud, but most of the Sage literature has not yet been installed in scientific editions.

PREPARATION OF SCHOLARLY EDITIONS

Creating a Scholarly edition involves several steps, including finding type witnesses, determining manuscript nature, establishing genealogy (when possible), collating manuscripts, selecting the type of edition (diplomatic, eclectic, synoptic), creating an exchange apparatus, and ensuring text accessibility to readers. In the past, these processes required extensive and laborious work, often with limited possibilities. However, the digital age offers researchers the opportunity to develop sophisticated digital scientific editions that streamline technical work and cater to the diverse needs of readers. Established repositories and new tools can significantly aid Jewish studies researchers in creating scientific editions of Hebrew texts. Examples of such tools include Transkibus and E-Scriptorium for transcription creation, as well as Dicta tools for building synopses and searching for sources.

DIGITAL SCHOLARLY EDITIONS

Technological advancements in computing over the past few decades have revolutionized the analysis of large databases and the extraction of meaningful conclusions (Schoch, 2013). Programming tools facilitate the representation of texts (Deegan-Sutherland and Sutherland, 2009), the identification of early texts combined with later ones (Bar-Asher Siegal and Shmidman, 2019), the development of advanced search engines (Shmidman, Koppel & Porat, 2018), digital text display, text-to-text linking, and more.

Elena Pierazzo's research has played a pivotal role in establishing a central research infrastructure for the preparation of digital scientific editions (Pierazzo, 2015).

The purpose of this poster is to present these innovations and emphasize the possibilities available to researchers in Jewish studies when undertaking the writing of a digital scientific publication.

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Modelling Roud's literary creation

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In this poster we present genetic networks of the poetic works of the Swiss writer and photographer Gustave Roud. A genetic network represents the relationships between publications and preparatory materials. Genetic networks address questions of scholarly editing, genetic criticism, and authorial philology.

Gustave Roud (1897-1976) is one of the most important French-speaking Swiss authors of the 20th century. The SNSF project “Gustave Roud. Œuvres complètes” (University of Lausanne, 2017-2021, directed by C. Jaquier and D. Maggetti). A web application (<https://roud.unil.ch>) complements the printed edition, providing access to the archival documents and other materials.

The project has developed the GENO ontology for describing genetic relationships in the form of networks (Christen and Spadini 2019; Spadini 2023; Spadini et al. 2023). With GENO 1.0 it is possible to describe genetic entities (the genetic dossier, publications and parts of them, avant-textual witnesses, diary entries, documentation, etc.) and their relationships (clustering, chronology, reuse, etc.). A list of genetic stages is available to differentiate avant-textual witnesses: (in alphabetical order) clear copy, draft, final copy, list, plan, proofs, published item, scenario, sketch. GENO can distinguish between endogenetic/exogenetic materials and composition phases by inference and it reuses FRBR entities.

The development of the ontology is inspired by representations of data found in digital scholarly editions, such as *Les manuscrits de Madame Bovary* (Girard et al. 2009), Hermann Burger, *Lokalbericht. Digitale Edition* (Dängeli et al. 2016), *Friedrich Dürrenmatt. Das Stoffe-Projekt* (Probst & Weber 2021), *Robinson de Paul Valéry: édition génétique* (Johansson et al. 2018). The importance of an explicit representation of the order and classification of the genetic material was expressed by Ferrer, who mentioned the need to “give names to the links” between documents⁷⁰. Identifying the genetic networks not only of a single work, but of many works linked by the reuse of materials was the challenge of the Roud project, in line with Van Hulle's proposal for an “entire œuvre's genetic dossier”⁷¹.

The project team collaborated with researchers from the DensityDesign Lab at the Politecnico di Milano to develop data visualisations to be included in the web application. The data visualisations represent the literary genesis, can guide users in browsing the materials and help scholars to identify patterns in the author's creative process (Elli et al. 2023).

A subset of JSON-LD data, limited to the genetic networks, was extracted from the entire project dataset using SPARQL queries. The prototyping, evaluation and implementation phases were based on the initial definition of common design requirements. The final outputs are ten visualisations in the form of sky maps (see Figure 1 and 2). The metaphor of the sky map was chosen to represent the interpretive distance that researchers maintain from the materials when they propose genetic relationships, as opposed to when they annotate the documents with more factual information such as year and place of publication. The night sky was also important to the author, who was inspired by long nocturnal walks.

⁷⁰ “Ce qui est sans doute à retenir de cette expérience [with the software Storyspace] [...] c'est la nécessité de *nommer* les liens et de prévoir des carrefours de liens” (Ferrer 2008, italics in the original).

⁷¹ “Traditionally, genetic criticism tends to approach an author's œuvre work by work. It would be useful to also consider a work's genesis within the development of the author's œuvre in its entirety, and consider all the geneses of its components, including vestigial notes, drafts and unpublished works, constituting the sous-œuvre [...] in the sense of the entire œuvre's genetic dossier” (Van Hulle 2022, 113).

Finally, we propose both the data model and the visualisation model for use in other projects: GENO is suitable for representing a wide variety of literary geneses and for accommodating different levels of description; the sky maps and the design process can be inspiring for other collaborative research efforts to support scholarly editing and literary scholarship.

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ORD-Xplore: Empowering Digital Librarians in Unifying Digital Editions

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INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM CHARACTERIZATION

Digital libraries focus on providing access to large collections of digital resources, such as digital scholarly editions (DSE). However, ensuring the standardization and interoperability among DSE poses as challenges. As the number of DSE grow, maintaining an overview becomes difficult. Digital librarians often lack resources to analyze edition data systematically, which hinders their ability to unify and standardize DSE projects accurately. In turn, digital librarians need to have a comprehensive understanding on how DSE can be linked together. To empower digital librarians, we present ORD-Xplore, an interactive visual analysis tool to explore connections between multiple DSE. ORD-Xplore is the result of an iterative and collaborative design process, together with digital librarians, edition coordinators, data curators, and visualization experts.

RELATED WORK

The challenge of linking DSE is multi-faceted and often difficult to achieve due to inherent problems with heterogeneous documents, high flexibility of TEI-XML (Chammas 2020), and different annotation practices, both within and across editions (Ioannides 2005). There is advocacy in literature suggesting other encoding formats such as RDF and JSON (Chammas 2020). However, these also do not solve the inherent issues with the heterogeneity of editions and different annotation practices. Another approach to address this challenge is working with existing formats and building tools to support digital librarians (Schlitz 2009). However, most solutions only support within-edition comparison (Baumann 2019), and only few approaches exist towards unifying multiple heterogeneous editions (Bleier 2018).

APPROACH

Our work utilizes a comprehensive corpus of six heterogeneous DSE encoded in TEI-XML from the Center for Digital Edition and Edition Analytics (ZDE) at the University of Zurich. A “bottom-up” data-centered approach would be to analyze common tags, and try to achieve comparability between digital editions in a labour-intensive, expert-driven process. Instead, we apply a top-down approach to support digital librarians in emphasizing on main connection types between editions. These connection types are **temporal**, **spatial**, and **textual** edition characteristics. The ORD-Xplore interface is composed of seven interactive and linked views (see Figure 1). The *Edition Details* present a legend of editions and ability to filter the editions across the interface. The *Digital Edition Connectivity View* visualizes the temporal, textual, and spatial links between digital editions using a node-link diagram. The *Temporal View* visualizes the temporal year data as found in the metadata from DSE using a timeline visualization. The *Geographical View* visualizes the spatial locations of documents on a map, which are extracted from the metadata and geo-located using Nominatim from OpenStreetMaps. The *Text View* visualizes the volume of metadata in each edition referring to editorial, figures, entities, media and the original text in a heatmap. The *Edition Similarity View* describes the similarity of two editions based on the temporal, textual and spatial connectivity in a bar chart. The *Document View* provides a hierarchy to visualize the document level granularity of DSE.

Figure 1: ORD-Xplore interface visualizing three digital editions with the temporal filter between 15th century to 17th century and location in central France.

With ORD-Xplore, librarians can, e.g., interactively filter for the 15th to 17th century and a particular geo location such as central France, to find editions corresponding to this information need. A librarian may also identify a lack of matching documents she is looking for; a signal that metadata annotations may be missing. Further, the librarian could visualize the spatial data, and outliers and could point to inaccurate geo location tagging.

VALIDATION, DISCUSSION, AND FUTURE WORK

We designed ORD-Xplore through an iterative user-centered design approach with librarians and other experts, accompanied with a workshop series at the DSI, Zürich. We evaluated the usefulness of ORD-Xplore in a summative user study with librarians, visualization experts, and non-experts. Limitations of ORD-Xplore are visual scalability issues for more than twenty editions, as well as its dependency on the quality of TEI-XML representations of editions. Also, librarians may want more fine-grained control over visual elements. Currently, the meta data about editions is analysed together with annotations on the original text. Giving control over this data may help derive more informed insights.

CONCLUSION

We presented ORD-Xplore, an visual analysis approach to bridge DSE using **temporal**, **textual**, and **spatial** connections. We iteratively designed and built ORD-Xplore in a multidisciplinary setting. We aim to empower digital librarians to explore and analyze multiple DSE, gain insights, and make better informed decisions towards the unification of editions.

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Proto4DigEd: Prototypical Workflows for Digital Editions

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GOALS

The main goal of this ORD project funded by swissuniversities is to test and further develop prototypical workflows in the conception phase of digital edition projects. The conception phase is particularly crucial from an ORD perspective: it is here that the foundations are laid for ensuring that research data remain accessible and can be re-used later.

Proto4DigEd answers to a growing need for standardisation: "The challenge here is to imagine what a Prêt-à-Porter edition might look like, that is, to model the digital editions of the future and their editors, or, better, the skills they need to acquire." (Pierazzo 2019, 214). For this aim, the project tests and documents the use of proven tools (Transkribus, TEI Publisher) using the planned digital letter edition PARES (see below) as an example. The involvement of various stakeholders and the national and international ORD community are of great importance.

Proto4DigEd is not only a model edition, but creates possibilities for exchanges between said stakeholders in workshops (see below). Besides these official events, Proto4DigEd is interested in low threshold exchanges and invites anybody interested to contact its coordinator: elias.zimmermann@uzh.ch

STRUCTURE

The project management is carried out by the *Romanisches Seminar UZH* (= RoSe, Prof. Dr Ursula Bähler) in collaboration with *Science IT UZH*. They represent the core team entrusted with the realisation and documentation of the prototypical workflows. The *Zentrum Digitale Editionen & Editionsanalytik UZH* (ZDE) is responsible for the national and international networking of the project as well as documenting the workflows in connection with long-term archiving. ZB Zürich brings expertise in data management on structured and standardised metadata and linking. The ZB intensifies its activities on research data management and especially digital editions, which is an important trend at large academic libraries. Based on the French corpus linking with the authority vocabulary of IdRef is incorporated (Ködel 2017). Linking to German sets (GND 2023) ensures interoperability across language boundaries. The head of the repository for humanities research data in Switzerland (the DaSCH) contributes her experience in interoperability and building long-term archives.

TOOLS AND PROJECT DESIGN

The project is not intended to develop new technical solutions, but rather to focus on connecting existing tools. For the automated transcription of manuscripts (HTR) Transkribus offers sophisticated general text recognition models as well as the training of specific models. TEI Publisher is a publishing toolbox developed in Switzerland and Germany that is supported by a growing community and allows standardised markup of texts in TEI-XML and their online publication.

The workflow is organised as part of an agile project design, i.e. small work packages are discussed and evaluated in close collaboration with all project participants at regular intervals. The resulting feedback loops enable the fastest possible corrections.

GREATER SCOPE: PARES

PARES (Gaston Paris: des archives aux réseaux, planned start in 2024) is a binationally conceived Swiss-French project that aims to make the entire archive of Gaston Paris digitally accessible and usable. Gaston Paris was one of the leading French philologists of the second half of the 19th century (Bähler 2004ff.). The project's centrepiece is the extensive correspondence of the scholar, who was in contact with around 1,800 correspondence partners from all over the world, which corresponds to a total corpus of around 27,000 pages. The connection between PARES and Proto4DigEd is twofold: 1. Shared data: Proto4DigEd uses data compiled in preparation for PARES (inventories of digitised documents, research on Gaston Paris' correspondence). Conversely, edited correspondence (TEI-XML data, ODD, frontend-solutions) created by Proto4DigEd can be reused by PARES.

2. Common workflows: PARES will also reuse workflows created by Proto4DigEd (even if the prototypical workflow of Proto4DigEd is not tailored to PARES alone). Conversely, the workflows of Proto4DigEd are informed by an earlier project

that prepares PARES: PHILINGK (2021-2023), a project of *RoSe* and the *University of Graz*, who edited the correspondence of Gaston Paris and the linguist Hugo Schuchardt (part of the digital Hugo Schuchardt Archive, Hurch 2022).

REUSABILITY AND WORKSHOPS

The results of the research project will be documented in the Gitlab instance at UZH. It is expected that the first outputs will be publicly available in spring 2024.

The first workshop (prototypical workflows) is planned on the **10th of April 2024 in Zurich**. The second workshop (long-term sustainability of data) is scheduled for the **11th of September 2024**. We will be happy to keep you informed about its details via the ZDE newsletter (<https://www.zde.uzh.ch/de/newsletter.html>).

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TEI Publisher: <https://teipublisher.com> (accessed 6.12.2023)

Transkribus: <https://readcoop.eu/de/transkribus/> (accessed 6.12.2023)

Heinrich Wölfflin – Gesammelte Werke (Digital Edition)

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INTRODUCTION

The Digital Edition of Heinrich Wölfflin – Gesammelte Werke (HWGW) is a collaborative effort between the Institute of Art History, University of Zurich and the Bibliotheca Hertziana – Max Planck Institute for Art History in Rome, to make available as Open Access a critical edition of all the published books and unpublished manuscripts by the renowned Swiss art historian. In order to achieve this, we developed together a workflow that try to ensure the long-term sustainability of the project.

ENCODING AND PLATFORMS

The digital edition is based on standards like TEI XML⁷² for the encoding of the content and the annotations, and open source / Community driven platforms for the transcription of the original content, the online visualization.

WORKFLOW

The digital edition workflow is developed as a sustainable way to ensure that the flow from original writings (in paper or digital images of the pages) to online critical annotated edition is easily adapted to any source that we are planning to host. TEI XML is beneficial for online critical edition, since it has all the flexibility needed to create the edition and there are open-source platforms, like TEI Publisher⁷³ that ease the conversion of the XML to HTML, made dynamic with standardized JavaScript and XQuery, for online reading.

Unfortunately, scholars are not used to write directly in XML so we had to develop:

- An easy way to convert the word processor documents that were initially used to help typesetting the print edition, with XSLT conversion of the markup to XML elements
- A reliable way to transcribe documents and have the transcription converted in TEI XML, with the help of the Transkribus Platform⁷⁴.
- Annotate and (in the future) comment on TEI file directly with the support of TEI Publisher Annotation

The use of separate TEI Publisher applications for annotation and publication decouple these two work areas and enable the scholars in easily annotating semantic connections to authority files like GND or GEONAMES to mark entities like people, places, organizations without interacting with configuring the Lucene engine behind eXist-db (the framework behind TEI Publisher)⁷⁵ for analyzing and retrieving these annotations across all volumes and manuscripts. The platform is not only open source, but actively and continuously developed, thus ensuring long term access to the digital edition.

The use of Transkribus platform is important for the paleographic transcription of the manuscript notebooks, but also because, compared to standard OCR of printed text, it allows for neural text and structure recognition that can be converted directly into structured TEI XML with the use of open-source scripts that we have combined to create a complete toolchain, *trans2tei*⁷⁶.

Extra steps have been taken to ensure the best usability of the platform interface, with a design that tries to overcome the stock design limitations⁷⁷.

Images are integrated in the publication both as facsimiles and as text figures with the integration of IIIF⁷⁸ standards to enhance the interoperability with other edition infrastructures.

⁷² Text Encoding Initiative, <https://tei-c.org/>.

⁷³ <https://teipublisher.com/index.html>.

⁷⁴ <https://readcoop.eu/transkribus/?sc=Transkribus>.

⁷⁵ <https://exist-db.org/>.

⁷⁶ <https://github.com/biblhertz/trans2tei/> (Bastianello and Baumgartner 2023).

⁷⁷ The new beta interface is accessible at <http://hwpreview.humanitiesconnect.pub/>.

⁷⁸ International Image Interoperability Framework <https://iiif.io/>.

FUTURE PLANS

HWGW is ready to work with Natural Language Processing and all the semantic annotations to Open Linked Data will ease the access to the content both for human and machine analysis. With linking between related documents, we want to make third-party commenting possible without altering the content. The platform is an open canvas that can potentially allow for continued studies.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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